

22IEM05 NEWSTAND

Report on the characterisation and calibration of transfer standard spectroradiometers from at least 5 end user applications (to enable the detector-based traceability of spectral irradiance measurements as an alternative to the incandescent lamps-based dissemination of the unit)

This report also includes i) the definition of the minimum requirements for relevant properties of (array) spectroradiometers to be suitable as transfer standards, ii) the development of procedures for their calibration that enable traceable measurements at end-user sites, and iii) the determination of uncertainties associated with the new traceability methods for spectral irradiance

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1 Introduction and scope

The accurate measurement of spectral irradiance is essential across various scientific research and industrial applications. Traditionally, spectral irradiance calibrations have relied on incandescent lamp-based transfer standards, such as FEL-type quartz tungsten-halogen (QTH) lamps, disseminated through National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and Designated Institutes (DIs). The project develops a detector-based dissemination of the unit of spectral irradiance using accurately calibrated array spectroradiometers. These instruments may be suitable as detector-based spectral irradiance transfer standard. The consortium members have characterized the relevant instrumental properties of a variety of array spectroradiometers provided to the consortium by stakeholders from a variety of scientific or industrial applications.

Accurate radiometric calibrations of the instruments took place at the NMIs and DIs facilities using well-established characterization methods, allowing direct traceability to the International System of Units (SI). Each consortium partner involved in this activity has produced a report on the characterizations in their laboratories. This deliverable reports the results of these characterizations and the methodology to follow for a complete calibration of array spectroradiometers to potentially be qualified as irradiance transfer standards. In addition to the characterization procedures and results, this report provides the analyses of retrieved instrumental parameters to be considered in the measurement process.

This report shows the results of various spectroradiometer calibrations and serves as a foundational step toward detector-based dissemination of the unit of spectral irradiance. The results provide the necessary groundwork for calculating the best estimation and uncertainty of a given measurement through the metrological digital twin to be developed in the project. The digital twin is a key to the detector-based metrological framework in the project and the calibrated instrumental properties are a critical input to this. Therefore, the calibration results in this report will support the alternative detector-based traceability framework of the project. These calculations done by the digital twin also help define best practices for implementing detector-based traceability across multiple end-user applications.

This report is structured according to the involved consortium partners. Each subsequent chapter presents their characterisation setups, methods and results from the characterization of spectroradiometers that are used in various end-user applications followed by discussions of challenges encountered during the work and lessons learned.

2 Characterization and calibration of spectroradiometers at Aalto

2.1 Spectroradiometer instruments calibrated

The characterized device, Avantes 'AvaSpec-UV/VIS/NIR', is a spectroradiometer based on line detectors for measuring spectral irradiance. It is composed of two internal halves, one for UV-visible light and another for infrared radiation. These two halves operate independently as USB-B connected devices, but the measurements can be combined by the operating software into a merged measurement, where both devices measure simultaneously. Light is collected by a diffuser head which connects to both devices through a split fiber optic cable. This specific device is used with short integration times to measure light pulses

The UV-visible half of the device provides measurement values from 175.4 nm to 1100.1 nm. However, the calibration only begins from the pixel at 200.172 nm and with no set responsivity, these shorter wavelengths produce very little readings even to stray light. The pixel wavelength step changes nearly linearly with wavelength from 0.604 nm in UV to 0.545 nm in near infrared.

The infrared half of the device provides measurement values from 925.3 nm to 1171.9 nm. The pixel wavelength step changes from 4.1 nm at shorter wavelengths to 3.679 nm in longer wavelengths.

2.2 Calibration setups and standards used

Calibrations were carried out at two setups at Aalto university. In the irradiance laboratory setup, a detector can be mounted on an optical rail in front of a reference light source, allowing for precise control of distance and positioning of the detector relative to the optical axis of the light source. During the measurements, the temperature was 22.6 ± 0.5 °C and the relative humidity was 32.7 ± 0.5 %.

In the laser laboratory setup, a linear translator moves a test detector and a reference detector in and out of a laser beam to compare the responses of the two detectors. A liquid crystal laser power controller allows varying the power for the measurement and stabilizes the laser. A beam splitter directs a portion of the controlled beam into a monitor detector which allows for correcting for any power fluctuations. During the measurements, the temperature was 22.4 ± 0.5 °C and the relative humidity was 28.2 ± 0.5 %.

2.3 Characterization methods, approaches

Linearity of the spectrometer was characterized using the laser laboratory setup, by measuring the spectroradiometer response compared to a calibrated silicon detector (UVFR-3) at various power levels. The light source used was a 543 nm HeNe laser. To prevent response fluctuations caused by speckle in the fiber connecting the detector head and the spectroradiometer, a spinning diffusive disc was placed in front of the spectroradiometer diffuser to destroy the laser coherence.

The measurement was repeated at two integration time settings, 2 ms typically used by the device owner, and 50 ms to see if it affects. The latter time was also used in the entrance plane determination.

Pixel wavelength assignment, or wavelength scale, was calibrated by measuring spectral lines of mercury and krypton pen lamps. Mercury emission lines were used for the UV-visible calibration, and Krypton emission lines for the infrared calibration. The peak positions for the measured emission lines were calculated as centroid wavelengths and compared to literature values.

Bandpass was determined as full width at half maximum of the mercury and krypton emission lines measured during the wavelength scale calibration.

Entrance plane position relative to the front of the spectrometer diffuser was determined by measuring the spectral intensity of a characterized FEL lamp (FEL-460) at distances from 500 mm to 700 mm in 10 mm steps. The entrance plane was determined by modelling the effect of the inverse square law, accounting for the lamp offset from reference plane, width of spectrometer aperture and the aperture reference plane. With the lamp offset known, and the aperture width measured, the aperture plane was fitted to minimize the deviation between the model and measurements. Nonlinearity was compensated for based on the linearity measurement.

Stray light was characterized by measuring a Xenon lamp through long pass filters and comparing the radiation detected in regions blocked by the filter with the dark values. For the visible range a long pass filter of 500 nm was used and for the IR region a long pass filter of 1400 nm was used. Stray light for an unfiltered measurement was estimated from the ratio of total irradiance for the filtered and unfiltered measurements.

Spectral responsivity was calibrated by measuring a characterized tungsten filament lamp FEL-460 at the distance of 500 mm. The measured spectral irradiance values were compared to the known values.

2.4 Results of characterizations

For linearity of power responsivity, the device was found to have significant nonlinearity at both low and high power. A polynomial fit was made for results both at 2 ms integration time and 50 ms integration time. These measurement results are presented in Figure 1. Results have been normalized to the maxima for comparison. With 2-ms integration time, the maximum was at the laser power level $P = 302.58 \text{ uW}$. With 50-ms integration time, the maximum was at the laser power level $P = 11.62 \text{ uW}$.

Figure 1: Relative responsivities of Avantes spectrometer normalized to the peak values.

The pixel wavelength assignment for the UV-visible half of the device was found to be well calibrated. As seen in Table 1, any wavelength correction would be smaller than the uncertainty, so no correction is needed. The reference values are based on natural constants, so the main uncertainty component for the UV-visible region is the standard deviation of 0.018 nm.

Table 1: Wavelength calibration for UV-visible, Strong emission lines of mercury.

Literature	253.651 nm	296.728 nm	404.656 nm	435.833 nm	546.074 nm
Measured	253.698 nm	296.712 nm	404.659 nm	435.845 nm	546.087 m
Deviation	0.006 nm	0.0158 nm	-0.003 nm	-0.003 nm	-0.010 nm
Standard Deviation, k = 2	0.0178				

For the infrared half of the device, a wavelength correction of +1.31 nanometers should be applied, seen in Table 2. This brings the measured values within the uncertainty, dominated by the standard deviation of 0.211 nm. The high uncertainty in the infrared region is caused by smaller krypton emission peaks, which are challenging to account for, due to the large wavelength step size and bandwidth of the device in the infrared region.

Table 2: Wavelength calibration for UV-visible, Strong emission lines of krypton.

Literature	975.176 nm	1181.930 nm	1442.679 nm
Measured	973.355 nm	1180.653 nm	1441.275 nm

Deviation	1.429 nm	1.193 nm	1.404 nm
Standard Deviation k = 2	0.211		

The bandpass for the UV-visible device is 2.36 nm and the bandpass for the infrared device is 7.19 nm.

The entrance plane is located 2.08 mm behind the front of the measurement head of the spectrometer. The measured values deviate from the inverse square law model by $\pm 0.25\%$, with a standard deviation of 0.12 %.

Stray light for the UV-visible part of the device, with a broadband source, causes a deviation of approximately 0.1 % as compared to the full signal at 500 nm with no filter in place as seen in Figure 2. However, approaching the far ends of the UV spectrum, stray light contributed up to 80 % of the signal.

Figure 2: Avantes spectroradiometer stray light in UV-Visible range.

The severity of stray light on at different wavelengths can be estimated from the wavelength dependent counts to irradiance transfer functions of the device, presented. Due to the extreme correction factors for the UV-visible device below 250 nm and above 1000 nm wavelength, results in these regions with broadband sources are highly unreliable as the signal is easily dominated by stray light.

In the infrared range stray light has a much more marginal effect and is largely lost to noise as seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Avantes spectroradiometer stray light in infrared range.

Spectral irradiance calibration revealed a discrepancy between the measured irradiance and that known from the known FEL-460 reference lamp. Additionally, there was a significant gap between the responsivity levels of the UV-visible and IR sides of the spectroradiometer as seen in Figure 4. To compensate for the difference, correction curves were fitted into the data based on the relative difference. A corrected measurement data was then produced and compared with the FEL-460 model values as seen in Figure 5. Significant offsets remain in the far ends of the UV-visible measurement but as they are a result of stray light, they should remain after a spectral irradiance correction.

Figure 4: Spectral irradiance measured with Avantes spectroradiometer compared with known irradiance from FEL-460 reference lamp at a distance of 500 mm.

Figure 5: Avantes spectroradiometer spectral irradiance measurement of FEL-460 lamp corrected for spectral sensitivity.

3 Characterization and calibration of spectroradiometers at CMI

3.1 Spectroradiometer instruments calibrated

The device characterized by CMI is the commercial HR8 fibre coupled spectrometer from the Czech company Narran. The spectrometer offers a spectral range from 200nm to 1200 nm. The HR8 sensor dynamic range can be changed by setting sensor integration time value from 10us to 2s. The HR8 is operated and powered through an USB interface. Narran kindly provided the software application with stored calibration values for both pixel to wavelength and for pixels spectral irradiance responsivity. It provided also libraries in the form of LabView functions for the software integration in CMI calibrations facilities. The input optics consists of a cosine diffuser to be connected to the end of the input optical fibre. The spectrometer uses a spectral diffracting element in conjunction with a ccd sensor with 3600 pixels.

The main application of the HR8 spectrometer is the spectral characterization of lasers emitting in the Si spectral range used for engraving, grooving, cutting and welding materials in the manufacturing industry.

3.2 Calibration setups and standards used

The spectral irradiance calibration of the spectrometer was performed with the spectral irradiance CMI facility based on standard irradiance filament lamp (PA 889) with direct traceability to the primary standard for irradiance based on black body. For the wavelength calibration and band pass function the narrowband tuneable source developed to fulfill the activity A1.3.1 was used. This tuneable source is traceable to the length standard by a calibrated wavemeter. The wavelength calibration and band pass function were performed automatically thanks to the software integration of the spectrometer in the CMI facility.

3.3 Characterization methods, approaches

The spectrometer software application from Narran was used to measure the spectral irradiance values calculated based on the calibration factors stored in the spectrometer device.

For the wavelength scale and bandpass calibrations, the CMI narrowband tunable source was used to illuminate the spectrometer entrance optics with a quasi-monochromatic (0.2 nm FWHM). A dedicated software read the spectrometer measured spectrum and calculated the peak position w_0 and the FWHM value using a Lorentzian function $L(w)$ to fit the measured data according to the following equation:

$$L(w) = \frac{A}{1 + \left(\frac{w - w_0}{FWHM/2}\right)^2}$$

3.4 Results of characterizations

The result of the spectral irradiance calibration of the spectrometer is reported in the table below with the relative standard uncertainty values expressed in percentage of the measured values.

Table 3: Results of the spectral irradiance performed by CMI on the Narran H38 spectrometer.

Wavelength	Spectral Irradiance	Measured spectral irradiance	Relative Unc U_c
	PA 889	spektrometr (DUT)	
λ	E_λ	E_λ	
[nm]	[mW m ⁻² nm ⁻¹]	[mW m ⁻² nm ⁻¹]	[%]
380	5,59	2,33	13,6
390	6,77	2,73	16,9

400	8,09	3,15	17,3
410	9,61	3,67	10,1
420	11,25	3,85	7,1
430	13,00	5,30	9,5
440	14,90	6,92	9,1
450	16,93	9,29	14,0
460	19,06	10,68	7,1
470	21,30	16,66	4,2
480	23,67	20,25	3,7
490	26,13	24,04	3,9
500	28,67	27,41	3,7
510	31,20	31,36	4,3
520	33,90	35,86	3,7
530	36,60	37,58	3,8
540	39,30	43,78	3,7
550	42,10	49,01	3,7
560	44,80	54,96	3,7
570	47,60	62,93	3,7
580	50,30	69,47	3,7
590	53,00	74,37	3,7
600	55,70	79,87	4,0
610	58,30	85,15	3,7
620	60,90	91,55	3,9
630	63,40	93,35	4,3
640	65,80	89,38	3,7
650	68,20	88,70	3,9
660	70,50	92,02	4,3
670	72,70	95,92	4,2
680	74,80	98,49	4,0
690	76,90	99,85	4,6
700	78,80	100,10	5,3
710	80,60	100,70	4,0
720	82,40	100,85	4,7
730	84,00	100,39	4,3
740	85,60	100,85	4,3

750	87,00	100,12	4,5
760	88,40	96,74	4,6

In the figures below we report the results for the wavelength scale calibration and bandpass characterization performed using the CMI narrowband tunable source-based facility.

Figure 6: Results of the Narran H38 spectrometer wavelength scale calibration performed by CMI narrowband tuneable source facility. In yellow the polynomial function used by Narran to calculate the wavelength from the pixel.

Figure 7: Results of the Narran H38 spectrometer bandpass measurement performed by CMI narrowband tuneable source facility.

3.5 Lessons learned

Some of the spectrometer internal calibration factors such as pixel to wavelength were accessible in the form of a polynomial function while others such as the pixel irradiance responsivity and linearity corrections were not easily available. The software library to control the spectrometer was not extensively documented and required multiple iterations to work properly.

4 Characterization and calibration of spectroradiometers at CSIC

4.1 Spectroradiometer instruments calibrated

ID for reporting	KM1000	Ava-CT	QE
Manufacturer	Konica Minolta	Avantes	Ocean Insight
Model	CS-1000A	AvaSpec-ULS2048-USB2-FCPC	QE-PRO
Owner	CSIC	CandelITEC	CandelITEC
Spectral range (nm)	380 - 780	300 – 1100	200 – 575
Spectral bandwidth (nm)	5	1,2	1,2
Spectral sampling interval (nm/pixel)	0,9	0,6	0,9
Number of channels	401	2048	1024
Irradiance optics	Cosine diffuser	Cosine diffuser	Cosine diffuser
Radiance optics	Macro lens and Standard lens (2° FOV)	No	No
Resolution ADC		16 bit	16 bit
Minimum integration / exposure time (ms)	40	1,05	8
Electrical power consumption (W)	Approx. 20 W (information for an upper model)	<5W	<15W
Size (cm x cm x cm)	14.6 × 14.8 × 25	17.5 x 11 x 4.4	18.5 x 11 x 4.7
Mass (kg)	4,7	0,5	1.15
Temperature stabilisation		No	Yes TE-cooled detector
Operating ambient temperature range (°C)	5 to 35		0 to 50
Control interface	RS-232C	USB	USB
Software interface	Matlab and commercial software	Manufacturer software	Manufacturer software
Output data format	Irradiance or radiance, ASCII	ASCII, Excel	ASCII, Excel
End-user applications	Measurement of CCT, irradiance, illuminance, chromaticity coordinates	Measurement of SPD, CCT, irradiance, illuminance, chromaticity coordinates, photobiological safety, calibration of radiometers	Measurement of SPD, irradiance, photobiological safety, calibration of radiometers

4.2 Calibration setups and standards used

The characterization and calibration setups used were different for the different characterizations:

- 4.2.1** For the **spectral responsivity** of the spectroradiometers, the spectral irradiance transfer standard lamps **OSRAM FEL**, with internal code IFA2 (for the spectroradiometer KM1000) and **Phillips G995 Z TIPO EG**, with internal code Z-1 (for Ava-CT and QE) were used.
- 4.2.2** For the **wavelength calibration**, the **Oriel Spectral Calibration Lamps** were used. Spectral lines of Hg were used for QE, and those of Ar, Hg and Kr for Ava-CT. For KM1000, a different procedure was used, using the same data as those obtained for characterizing the LSF.
- 4.2.3** The **Line Spread Function (LSF)** was evaluated using the monochromator available for spectral responsivity calibrations at IO-CSIC. It consists of a Laser Driven Light Source (Energetiq EQ-77-QZ-S LDLS) and a single-monochromator (ACTON Research Spectra PRO-500).
- 4.2.4** The **linearity** was evaluated using capabilities of the goniospectrophotometer available at IO-CSIC for bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) calibrations. Specifically, it was used (1) the directional and uniform irradiance provided by the combination of a Xe lamp and Köhler system, and the attenuation system based on the neutral density filters.
- 4.2.5** The determination of the **measurement plane** with respect to a reference plane was evaluated in the photometric bench (LS-ACS-T120ME) for calibration of illuminance meters and light sources. A luminous intensity transfer standard lamp (OSRAM 64222 (internal code BI-14F), $I = 1,555$ A, $I_V = 8,88$ cd, CCT = 2856 K) was used for irradiating the spectroradiometers.

All the characterizations were performed between 22 °C and 25 °C.

4.3 Characterization methods, approaches

4.3.1 Spectral responsivity

It was characterized by comparing with the net response of the spectroradiometers the irradiance produced by our spectral irradiance transfer standard lamps at a distance of 50 cm. For this characterization it is necessary to have well determined the position of the measurement plane, which needs to be located at 50 cm with respect to the reference plane of the transfer standard. This procedure was validated and CSIC provides a service with CMC. This characterization is carried out at only a specific irradiance level. It is important to verify previously that nonlinearity issues do not prevent the spectroradiometer from being used at that level. Therefore, it is convenient to carry out before the nonlinearity characterization. The responsivity as a function of the wavelength, together with its expanded uncertainty are represented in Figure 8 (Ava-CT), Figure 9 (QE) and Figure 10 (KM1000).

4.3.2 Wavelength calibration

The standard procedure used (CMC) consists of comparing the wavelength of the **Oriel Spectral Calibration Lamps** (Ground truth, GT, wavelengths, λ_c) with those observed in the spectroradiometer as wavelength (λ_m) of the maximum values of the identified peaks (spectroradiometer wavelengths). When a systematic deviation is observed, it is corrected by using a fitting function. In Figure 11 and Figure 12, the relative deviations of the GT and spectroradiometer wavelength and the fitting functions are shown for Ava-CT and QE. These fittings allow you to correct this deviation and correct the wavelength. The standard deviation of the residuals obtained after the correction is considered as the standard uncertainty of the corrected wavelength (λ_c). We consider it the same for all the spectral range. We used an alternative procedure for KM1000. In this case, the irradiation wavelengths of the calibrated monochromator used for characterizing LSF was used as GT wavelength. It allows more evaluation wavelength to be available, and to calibrate the wavelength and to characterize the LSF in a single procedure. The drawback is that we have to consider the wavelength uncertainty of the monochromator, which may increase the wavelength uncertainty of the spectroradiometer. In Figure 13, the

relative deviation of the GT and spectroradiometer wavelength is shown for KM1000. In Table 4, the correction applied for each spectroradiometer and the uncertainty after correction is shown.

4.3.3 Line Spread Function (LSF) characterization

The spectroradiometers were irradiated with different wavelengths with the monochromator, within their corresponding spectral range. **The slit size must be narrow enough that narrowing it more would not produce change in the normalized spectra.** In Figure 14, Figure 17 and Figure 19, the LSF matrix is represented for spectroradiometers Ava-CT, QE and KM1000, while in Figure 16, Figure 18, Figure 20 the LSF is shown for a central wavelength. The LSF is defined as normalized to the peak of each individual spectrum, once the dark signal was subtracted. We considered that the main source of uncertainty of the LSF is the nonlinearity, since the LSF profile contains more than two decades of significant values. In consequence, we used as an estimation of the value of relative uncertainty, the relative deviation from nonlinearity. This value depends on the net signal (s), and we obtained a fitting function $f_{NL}(s)$. The absolute uncertainty of the LSF is then expressed as:

$$u(LSF) = f_{NL}(s) \times LSF \quad (1)$$

An example of this uncertainty is expressed as a matrix in Figure 15, for Ava-CT.

4.3.4 Linearity

A methodology consisting of two methods for the characterization of the nonlinearity was used. The first one analyses it as a function of the response (number of net counts measured by the detector) and the integration time. The second one characterizes the nonlinearity as a function of irradiance. This methodology allows to identify the different sources of nonlinearity in relation to integration time, direct response of the instrument and irradiance to which the instrument is exposed. As a result, it is possible to establish the range of response and integration time usable for accurate irradiance measurements, and to obtain empirical functions to correct the nonlinearity from the different error sources.

4.3.4.1 Nonlinearity with respect to response and integration time

To analyse the nonlinearity with respect to the direct response of the instrument and the integration time, we worked with several different irradiance levels on the spectroradiometer, obtained by modifying the aperture of the optical system, a xenon lamp with a Köhler system producing a uniform irradiance on the detector measurement area. The full range of integration times available in the devices is evaluated. By adjusting the number of acquisitions to be averaged, the total exposure time was kept constant while modifying the integration time. This ensures that the number of photons collected by the detector is constant regardless of the integration time used, and consequently the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is approximately constant. It was hypothesized that, in a linear detector, the dark-subtracted response (net response) divided by the integration time should remain constant for a fixed irradiance level. To test this, key variables such as average net counts, standard deviation, average irradiance and standard error of irradiance were calculated. These variables allow us to characterize not only the average detector response, but also the scatter and uncertainty associated with the measurements. In this method, graphical representations were made to illustrate and analyse the results obtained. These representations allow to evaluate the nonlinear behaviour of the spectroradiometers as a function of integration time and signal response, and to identify the key dependences. In particular, plots have been generated showing the normalized irradiance as a function of integration time and of the signal corrected for dark noise, in order to identify the key variable causing the nonlinearity, if possible. These dependences are shown in Figure 21 and Figure 22, for Ava-CT, and in Figure 25 and Figure 26 for QE. This method is only applicable for spectroradiometers where the integration time can be selected freely by the user (Ava-CT, QE) and allow the proper acquisition conditions to be determined. In other cases, as with KM1000, this method cannot be applied because the integration time is selected automatically based on the irradiance level. In this case, second order nonlinearities (residuals from the nonlinearity corrections by the manufacturer) would be identified when following the second method below.

4.3.4.2 Nonlinearity with respect to irradiance

In this analysis, the nonlinearity of array spectroradiometers with respect to the irradiance was investigated using three different levels obtained by means of neutral density filters (ND filters) transmitting 100% (no ND filter), 10% and 1% the incident light, respectively. The transmittance (ratio between counts measured with and without filter) of another filter with a transmittance of around 40 % was measured three times with the spectroradiometer to be characterized, one for each irradiance level. The hypothesis is that the calculated transmittance must be constant if the detector is linear, regardless of the irradiance level. A deviation from this behaviour is regarded as caused by nonlinearity. Integration times were selected to avoid detector saturation and maximize the measured signal while minimizing noise. Again, by adjusting the number of acquisitions to be averaged, the total exposure time was kept constant while modifying the integration time. The uncertainties associated with the irradiance measurements were calculated using error propagation methods, which made it possible to evaluate the reliability of the obtained deviations. These include the relative deviation with respect to the highest irradiance level as a function of wavelength, for the three selected levels, and on the other hand, the transmittance calculated as a function of wavelength, evaluating the expected linearity for an ideal detector. Results for the three evaluated spectroradiometers are shown in Figure 23, Figure 24, Figure 27, Figure 28, Figure 29 and Figure 30.

4.3.5 Determination of the distance of the measurement plane with respect to the reference plane

In the photometric bench, the spectroradiometers are irradiated under constant irradiances at six different distances, d , (0.6 m, 1 m, 1.5 m, 2 m, 2.5 and 3 m) with respect to a reference plane in at the spectroradiometer, and the net signal is acquired. The hypothesis is that the measurement plane is for which the inverse-square law fulfils. Therefore, the equation

$$S = \frac{I}{(d + \delta)^2} \quad (2)$$

where S is the spectral average of the net signals, d is the distance to the reference plane, and I and δ are empirical parameters, is used to obtain δ , which represent the distance between the distance of the measurement plane with respect to the reference plane. Results of the values obtained for Ava-CT and QE are shown in Table 5.

4.4 Results of characterizations

4.4.1 Characterization of spectral responsivity (Figures and Tables)

Figure 8: [Ava-CT] Spectral responsivity (top) and expanded uncertainty of the spectral responsivity.

Figure 9: [QE] Spectral responsivity (top) and expanded uncertainty of the spectral responsivity.

Figure 10: [KM1000] Spectral responsivity (top) and expanded uncertainty of the spectral responsivity.

4.4.2 Wavelength calibration (Figures and Tables)

Table 4: Correction obtained after wavelength calibration.

ID	Correction	Standard uncertainty after correction
KM1000	$\lambda_c = (\lambda_m - 0.18) \text{ nm}$	0.88 nm
Ava-CT	$\lambda_c = (\lambda_m - 0.43) \text{ nm}$	0.082 nm
QE	$\lambda_c = (1.0013 \times \lambda_m - 0.8665) \text{ nm}$	0.046 nm

Figure 11: [QE] Relative difference between measured and ground-truth wavelength vs. the measured wavelength.

Figure 12: [Ava-CT] Relative difference between measured and ground-truth wavelength vs. the measured wavelength.

Figure 13: [KM1000] Relative difference between measured and ground-truth wavelength vs. the measured wavelength.

4.4.3 Characterization of the Line Spread Function, LSF (Figures and Tables)

4.4.3.1 Ava-CT spectroradiometer

Figure 14: [Ava-CT] Measured LSF matrix. Decimal logarithm is represented according to colour bar on the right. The values are previously normalized to the maximum value of the spectrum acquired at every irradiation wavelength.

Figure 15: [Ava-CT] Standard uncertainty of the measured LSF matrix shown in Figure 14.

Figure 16: [Ava-CT] Example of LSF distribution for a central wavelength.

4.4.3.2 QE spectroradiometer

Figure 17: [QE] Measured LSF matrix. Decimal logarithm is represented according to colour bar on the right. The values are previously normalized to the maximum value of the spectrum acquired at every irradiation wavelength.

Figure 18: [QE] Example of LSF distribution for a central wavelength.

4.4.3.3 KM1000 spectroradiometer

Figure 19: [KM1000] Measured LSF matrix. Decimal logarithm is represented according to color bar on the right. The values are previously normalized to the maximum value of the spectrum acquired at every irradiation wavelength.

Figure 20: [KM1000] Example of LSF distribution for a central wavelength.

4.4.4 Characterization of the linearity (Figures and Tables)

4.4.4.1 Ava-CT spectroradiometer

Figure 21: [Ava-CT] Normalized irradiance versus integration time for three different irradiance levels. Spectral averages are shown.

Figure 22: [Ava-CT] Normalized irradiance versus dark-subtracted signals for three different irradiance levels. Spectral averages are shown.

Figure 23: [Ava-CT] Relative deviation with respect to the highest level of the reference filter.

Figure 24: [Ava-CT] Mean relative transmittance ratio per level vs. mean irradiance (without filter) per level.

4.4.4.2 QE spectroradiometer

Figure 25: [QE] Normalized irradiance versus integration time for three different irradiance levels. Spectral averages are shown.

Figure 26: [QE] Normalized irradiance versus dark-subtracted signals for three different irradiance levels. Spectral averages are shown.

Figure 27: [QE] Relative deviation with respect to the highest level of the reference filter.

Figure 28: [QE] Mean relative transmittance ratio per level vs. mean irradiance (without filter) per level.

4.4.4.3 KM1000 spectroradiometer

Figure 29: [KM1000] Relative deviation with respect to the highest level of the reference filter.

Figure 30: [KM1000] Mean relative transmittance ratio per level vs. mean irradiance (without filter) per level.

4.4.5 Determination of the measurement plane with respect to the reference plane (Figures and Tables)

Table 5: Measurement of the difference between the reference plane (R) and the measurement plane (M), denoted as δ .

ID	δ / mm	$U(\delta)$ / mm
Ava-CT	15,1	1,4
QE	9,83	0,86

4.5 Conclusions and lessons learned

Some conclusions and lessons were drawn after the work done on spectroradiometer characterizations during this activity:

1. It is important to characterize nonlinearity before calibration of spectral responsivity or LSF characterization in order to avoid using conditions, as for instance a too short integration time, which might produce uncorrectable artefact in the signal.
2. A monochromator well calibrated in wavelength can be used for both calibrating wavelength and LSF of the spectroradiometers in a single procedure.
3. As a general comment, fully-automated procedures are possible and very beneficial for the complete calibration of spectroradiometer. This is much more time efficient and reduce the potential errors from manual acquisition of individual spectra.
4. The uncertainty of the LSF must, in our opinion, be related mainly to the nonlinearity of the spectroradiometer, since it may affect significantly the profile of the LSF, with a wide range of signals.
5. We determined the distance between a reference plane and the measurement plane using the inverse square law (from 0.6 m to 3 m), and we obtained uncertainties of around 1 mm. This uncertainty might be decreased using more positions and shorter distances. Actually, it should be done when the spectral responsivity is done at the calibration distance. A more practical procedure, which would decrease the potential error, is to characterize the position of the measurement plane at the moment of the calibration of the spectral responsivity. It can be done by mounting the spectroradiometers on a linear stage (preferably motorized) and acquiring spectra at different relative distances around the position of the calibration. This procedure might be fully automated.
6. According to some of the previous conclusions, a complete procedure for calibrating spectroradiometers in irradiance might be established in the following order: (1) Nonlinearity characterization, (2) Spectral responsivity calibration, with previous characterization, in the same setup, of the position of the measurement plane; and (3) Method for simultaneous LSF characterization and wavelength calibration using a monochromator calibrated in wavelength.

5 Characterization and calibration of spectroradiometers at IPQ

5.1 Spectroradiometer instruments calibrated

The device that IPQ aimed at characterizing was the commercial Instrument Systems CAS140D157U1B spectroradiometer from Instrument Systems. It has a 250 lines per nanometer grating, working in the 199 nm to 832 nm interval. The characterization consisted of using IPQ's spectroradiometer which is a very similar spectroradiometer to the one to be studied: a CAS140D156U2B spectroradiometer from Instrument Systems. It has a 250 lines per nanometer grating, working in the 288 nm to 1102 nm interval.

5.2 Calibration setups and standards used

The spectral irradiance measurements for the calibration of the spectroradiometer were performed with the IPQ spectroradiometer and the set of IPQ's luminous intensity primary standard lamps.

So far, at the IPQ Radiometry laboratory, no facility exists to perform the wavelength calibration and determine the band pass function of such spectroradiometers.

5.3 Characterization methods, approaches

Spectral irradiance measurements were performed with the photometric bench, as can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 31: the photometric bench with the standard photometer P 15 F0T head from LMT, and, on the other hand, the luminous intensity primary standard lamps

The detectors of spectroradiometers are mounted, next to the IPQ's standard photometer LMT P 15 F0T head, traceable to SI through its calibration by the le Cnam-LNE Photometry Laboratory, like the IPQ's luminous intensity primary standard lamps.

The purpose of the set up is to compare the integrated quantities the measurements of which are traceable to SI, with the result of the integration of the corresponding spectral quantities measured by the spectroradiometers. However, as both spectroradiometers are not yet wavelengths-calibrated, the results are unable to be displayed.

5.4 Results of characterization

As the accessories to perform the wavelength calibration of the spectroradiometers are needed, the results of the spectral irradiance measurements, performed in the end of 2024 December, are still incomplete. Examples

of spectral irradiance raw data, for the common [288; 832] nm spectral interval, measured by the 2 spectroradiometers, illuminated by one of the IPQ luminous intensity standard lamp are given for a 600 ms integration time:

And 200 ms integration time:

6 Characterization and calibration of spectroradiometers at LNE and le Cnam

6.1 Spectroradiometer instruments calibrated

An Avantes spectroradiometer from TUBITAK and an Ocean Optics spectroradiometer from LNE stakeholder were calibrated.

Two other spectroradiometers from TUBITAK were considered, a StellarNet EPP2000-UVN-SR model which never communicated with the PC and an ASEQ LR1 model which proved to be of very poor quality with no order filter. These two spectroradiometers are not included in this report.

Manufacturer	Avantes	Ocean Optics
Model	AvaSpec-PCT2048CL	Ocean NR
Wavelength range	190 nm – 450 nm	900 nm – 1700 nm
Optical fiber	UV-VIS-Ø200µm	VIS-NIR-Ø600µm
Entrance optic	Ø 3.9 mm quartz diffuser	UV-J1002-SMA-SHUT CMS Schreder entrance optics
CCD type	Hamamatsu S11639 , CMOS linear array	NC
Pixels	2048	512
Communication	USB	USB
SDK / DLL	AvaSpec 9.14	Ocean Direct 2.4.1

For this task, the responsivity of the Ocean Optics spectroradiometer was calibrated with le Cnam's high-temperature blackbody.

The Avantes spectroradiometer is an instrument optimised for the UV spectral range. The Ocean Optics is an instrument equipped with a SWIR CCD for measurements in the near infrared.

All measurements are carried out using the SDK/DLL supplied by the spectroradiometer manufacturer and calibration software developed by LNE for its calibration service.

6.2 Calibration setups, standards and methods used

All measurements are carried out in an air-conditioned laboratory at $23^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$.

6.2.1 Spectral scale

Spectral calibration involves assigning an average wavelength to each of the pixels making up the spectroradiometer. LNE uses spectral lamps to perform this calibration. This method is simple and does not require expensive equipment, but it does not cover the entire spectral range of the spectroradiometer, and the calibration depends on the wavelengths associated with each lamp.

The reference wavelengths and line levels are taken from the database managed by NIST [12].

Each lamp is acquired by subtracting the associated dark signal and taking care not to saturate the peaks. The level of each of the peaks measured is adjusted so that they are approximately all similar by adjusting the integration time or by modifying the distance between the source and the spectroradiometer. This is necessary on poor quality spectroradiometers where the peaks are asymmetric, resulting in a spectral shift as a function of peak height! In the large majority of cases, the spectral shift is independent of the peak height or is negligible.

The wavelength of the measured peak is determined by calculating its central length at mid-peak height.

Figure 32: 435 nm Hg line – Avantes AvaSpec mini spectroradiometer – FWHM 0,62 nm – spectral shift 0,25 nm.

Figure 33: 1129 nm Hg line – Ocean Optics NR spectroradiometer – FWHM 3,3 nm – spectral shift 2,5 nm.

The experimental measurements are compared with a theoretical spectrum, which can be calculated in two different methods.

The reference wavelength is the weighted average of the intensities of the reference wavelengths over an interval defined by the user, but which must remain between the value of the spectral bandwidth of the spectroradiometer and twice this value. Depending on the number of reference peaks selected, it is possible to calculate a standard deviation representative of the spectral range of the peaks.

It is also possible to calculate a theoretical spectrum from the wavelengths of each of the spectroradiometer's pixels, its spectral bandwidth and the values and intensities of the theoretical peaks. The instrument function can be adjusted according to the results obtained, but a triangular function, which corresponds to the convolution product of two rectangular slits, is the function that will most often match the experimental results. This type of spectrum is shown in Figure 32 and Figure 33. For some spectroradiometers it is more realistic to use a rectangular function. The wavelength of the reference peak is determined in the same way as with the experimental spectrum using a lamp.

The combination of these two methods makes it possible to consolidate the spectral calibration by adding an experimental uncertainty.

A standard uncertainty based on a rectangular distribution of the wavelength difference between two adjacent pixels must be added.

6.2.2 Dynamic linearity

Dynamic linearity consists of characterising the count response of the spectroradiometer as a function of the incident flux. This measurement must be made with a constant integration time to be totally independent of temporal linearity.

The method used by most manufacturers to measure dynamic linearity by modifying the integration time should be avoided.

Since dynamic linearity is mainly due to the CCD read-out circuit, we assume that the dynamic linearity of all pixels is the same, since there is only one read-out circuit on this type of CCD. It is also assumed that dynamic linearity is independent of wavelength. Consequently, all the pixels are used and considered as a single detector.

Dynamic linearity is measured using the addition flux method. The advantage of this method is that it is simple, easily covers the low dynamic range of spectroradiometers compared with a conventional photo-current detector and does not depend on a reference.

Figure 34: Addition flux method.

The method used at LNE involves a halogen lamp illuminating two circular half-apertures. The light is then focused by a condenser into an integrating sphere to collect all the flux. A system of masks makes it possible to block one or other of the apertures, neither of them, then both apertures to create a dark. The signal measured by the spectroradiometer on each of the two apertures is noted S_a and S_b , the signal measured through the two apertures is noted S_{a+b} and the dark S_o . A detector is linear if $S_a + S_b - 2.S_o = S_{a+b} - S_o$. The integration time or source power must be adjusted so that the S_{a+b} signal covers the full dynamic range of the spectroradiometer. The bench must be set so that $S_a = S_b$. All the pixels are used, each covering a different dynamic range. Spectroradiometer manufacturers agree to divide the signal by the linearity error to calculate the corrected signal.

The linearity error is then written as $d = \frac{S_{a+b} - S_o}{S_a + S_b - 2.S_o}$.

Only the standard deviations of the four measurements and the signal resolution contribute to the linearity uncertainty.

6.2.3 Temporal linearity

Temporal linearity involves characterising the spectroradiometer's count response as a function of integration time at constant signal. This measurement must be carried out at constant signal to be totally independent of dynamic linearity. Since temporal linearity is mainly due to the CCD synchronisation circuit, we assume that the temporal linearity of all the pixels is identical. It is also assumed that temporal linearity is independent of wavelength. Consequently, all the pixels are used and considered as a single detector.

Temporal linearity is measured using an adjustable radiance sphere, assuming that the relative spectral distribution of the source does not change with the radiance level. Care should be taken to ensure that the equipment used meets this criterion as closely as possible.

The measurement involves varying the integration time and adjusting the radiance source that the spectroradiometer signal is always the same. Measuring temporal linearity depends on the dynamic linearity of the source's photodetector. As far as possible, the measured spectrum should remain in the linear part of the dynamic linearity to minimise errors and corrections.

T is the integration time of the spectroradiometer and S the signal from the radiance source photodetector. The spectroradiometer will be linear if $T \times S = \text{Constant}$.

The uncertainties are the standard deviations of the spectroradiometer measurement, the standard uncertainty of the photodiode measurement with its standard deviation as the main factor, and the calibration of the current measurement instruments.

6.2.4 Stray light

Stray light from spectroradiometers is characterised by illuminating the system with a monochromatic source and measuring the spectroradiometer signal using the High Dynamic Range (HDR) method. This method is described in [6] and [14].

To generate monochromatic radiation, LNE uses several monochromators to cover the entire spectral range from UV to NIR. Because of the stray radiation generated by a monochromator, it is preferable to use a double monochromator to minimise this type of defect.

The spectral bandwidth of the monochromator should be as small as possible and smaller than that of the spectroradiometer so as not to artificially widen its spectral bandwidth and generate a spectrum of stray light from too wide a range of wavelengths. All these constraints sometimes make this measurement impossible due to a lack of incident power.

The measurement is carried out approximately every ten pixels, less if rapid variations in stray radiation are observed. Acquisition uses the HDR method, with several acquisitions up to 1000 times the nominal integration time (unsaturated peak). The rest of the pixels are calculated by linear interpolation.

An example of measurement is shown in the following three figures.

Figure 35: Unsaturated peak corrected for dark and spectrum corrected for dark by multiplying the integration times by 10.

Figure 36: Each spectrum is divided by the integration times, and the result is normalised to 1.

Figure 37: Result of the spectrum, called the line spread function.

The processing of the measurements and the calculation of the correction matrix are described in the publications listed at the beginning of this section.

The treatment of uncertainties is complex and has already been described in several European contracts, including the ENV03 SOLARUV contract.

6.2.5 Responsivity

Spectral responsivity is used to define a radiometric scale for the dynamics of the spectroradiometer. In most cases, and in the case of the NEWSTAND project, the radiometric scale is spectral irradiance ($W/(m^2 \cdot nm)$). Depending on the accessories associated with the spectroradiometer, it is possible to calibrate a spectroradiometer in intensity, luminance or spectral radiance.

In the case of irradiance, responsivity is expressed in $count/((W \cdot s)/(m^2 \cdot nm))$. Since responsivity depends on integration time, its responsivity is reduced to 1 s.

The spectral irradiance calibration of a spectroradiometer is usually determined using the spectral irradiance produced by a FEL halogen lamp, a deuterium lamp and an LDLS lamp. All these lamps operate in free fields.

The spectroradiometer is placed directly in front of the FEL lamp and its calibration is used to determine the spectral responsivity of the spectroradiometer.

If the spectroradiometer is sufficiently sensitive, the same operation is carried out with the deuterium lamp.

The spectroradiometer is also placed in front of the LDLS lamp (type EQ-99) at a distance of approximately 30 cm. This lamp is calibrated for spectral irradiance under the same conditions as the FEL lamp and the deuterium lamp. The comparator used is a type OL756 double monochromator.

A high-temperature blackbody BB3500M at $2700^\circ C$ was used to calibrate the Ocean Optics NIR spectroradiometer. It is therefore possible to calibrate a spectroradiometer using a primary spectral irradiance reference. Economically, this is not the best method, but for the calibration of reference spectroradiometers in the visible and near infrared, this equipment avoids the need to develop new transfer sources.

The spectroradiometer is calibrated at several integration times covering its full dynamic range and with at least two sources of different spectral distribution if the spectral range is compatible. Measurements are corrected for dynamic linearity, temporal linearity, spectral shift and, if possible, stray light. Several series with the same configuration are carried out. The different responsivities calculated take into account all the previous calibrations, and the differences observed are partly due to the uncertainties of these different calibrations.

A simplification of the uncertainties consists in considering that the standard uncertainty of the different responsivities is the contribution of all the different uncertainty components of the spectroradiometer. This

approach simplifies the uncertainty calculation and gives a representative view of the final uncertainty compared with a more rigorous method [11].

6.3 Results of characterization

6.3.1 Spectral scale

The two red lines represent the wavelength difference between two adjacent pixels in the spectral range of the spectroradiometer.

Figure 38: Avantes AvaSpec-PCT2048CL spectral calibration.

Table 6: Avantes AvaSpec-PCT2048CL spectral calibration

Lamp	Reference wavelength [nm]	Measure wavelength [nm]	Spectral shift [nm]	Expanded uncertainty [nm]
Hg	265,34	265,50	-0,16	0,10
Hg	289,36	289,59	-0,23	0,10
Hg	296,73	296,96	-0,23	0,10
Cd	298,08	298,32	-0,25	0,10
Hg	302,20	302,41	-0,21	0,10
Cd	308,11	308,32	-0,21	0,10
Cd	313,32	313,57	-0,25	0,10
Tl	322,98	323,21	-0,24	0,10
Cd	325,25	325,50	-0,25	0,10
Cd	326,11	326,37	-0,27	0,10
Zn	328,23	328,48	-0,25	0,10
Zn	330,27	330,52	-0,25	0,10

Hg	334,15	334,40	-0,25	0,10
Zn	334,51	334,76	-0,25	0,10
Cd	350,00	350,24	-0,24	0,10
Tl	351,92	352,18	-0,25	0,10
Tl	351,92	352,18	-0,25	0,10
Tl	377,57	377,83	-0,26	0,10
Hg	404,66	404,90	-0,24	0,10
Hg	407,78	408,03	-0,24	0,10
Hg	435,83	436,09	-0,25	0,10
Cd	441,30	441,55	-0,25	0,10

Figure 39: Ocean Optics Ocean NR spectral calibration.

Table 7: Ocean Optics Ocean NR spectral calibration.

Lamp	Reference wavelength [nm]	Measure wavelength [nm]	Spectral shift [nm]	Expanded uncertainty [nm]
Ar	912,30	914,57	-2,27	0,96
Ar	965,78	968,14	-2,36	0,94
Cs	1002,44	1004,41	-1,98	0,99
Cs	1012,36	1014,33	-1,97	0,96
Hg	1013,97	1016,41	-2,44	0,96
Ar	1047,01	1049,48	-2,46	0,95
Zn	1105,4	1107,8	-2,4	1,0

Hg	1128,71	1131,23	-2,52	0,93
Tl	1151,28	1153,62	-2,34	0,93
Ar	1244,49	1246,54	-2,05	0,95
Ar	1295,7	1298,1	-2,4	1,0
Tl	1301,32	1303,65	-2,33	0,92
Ar	1336,71	1339,18	-2,47	0,97
Ar	1350,41	1352,77	-2,37	0,91
Hg	1350,56	1352,77	-2,21	0,92
Hg	1357,02	1359,34	-2,32	0,93
Cs	1358,83	1361,28	-2,45	0,97

6.3.2 Dynamic linearity

A polynomial regression is calculated from the results of the linearity measurement. The measurement uncertainty is greater than 2% at levels below 5% of the spectroradiometer's dynamic range, around 1% at around 10% of the dynamic range and decreasing to 0.1% at 100% of the dynamic range.

Figure 40: Avantes AvaSpec-PCT2048CL dynamic linearity.

Table 8: Avantes AvaSpec-PCT2048CL dynamic linearity coefficients

Intercept	1,000932108
1st Coef	-4,41464E-07
2^{sd} Coef	-8,21555E-10
3rd Coef	5,95383E-13
4th Coef	-1,34242E-16
5th Coef	1,29812E-20

6 th Coef	-5,74645E-25
7 th Coef	9,52897E-30

No regression coefficient has been stored in the Avantes spectroradiometer. This is unusual for this manufacturer, but this calibration is an option when ordering the instrument.

Figure 41: Ocean Optics Ocean NR dynamic linearity.

Table 9: Ocean Optics Ocean NR dynamic linearity coefficients.

Intercept	0,992126398
1 st Coef	3,95216E-06
2 ^{sd} Coef	-6,67708E-10
3 rd Coef	5,04491E-14
4 th Coef	-1,92266E-18
5 th Coef	3,8899E-23
6 th Coef	-3,99427E-28
7 th Coef	1,63573E-33

6.3.3 Temporal linearity

Figure 42: Avantes AvaSpec-PCT2048CL temporal linearity.

There is no temporal nonlinearity with the Avantes AvaSpec-PCT2048CL spectroradiometer.

Figure 43: Ocean Optics Ocean NR temporal linearity.

Table 10: Ocean Optics Ocean NR temporal linearity coefficients

Integration time (ms)	Linearity correction
32	1,005
64	1,002
128	1,000

256	1,000
512	0,998
1024	0,995
2048	0,993
4096	0,989

6.3.4 Stray light

For greater clarity, the graphs show only an extract of the measurements.

Figure 44: Avantes AvaSpec-PCT2048CL line spread function.

Figure 45: Ocean Optics Ocean NR line spread function.

6.3.5 Responsivity

Figure 46: Avantes AvaSpec-PCT2048CL responsivity.

Table 11: Avantes AvaSpec-PCT2048CL uncertainty of responsivity.

Spectral range	Expanded uncertainty
225 nm – 230 nm	20%
230 nm – 235 nm	15%
235 nm – 240 nm	9,5%
240 nm – 250 nm	5,0%
250 nm – 290 nm	3,0%
290 nm – 400 nm	2,0%
400 nm – 460 nm	2,5%

Figure 47: Ocean Optics Ocean NR responsivity.

Table 12: Ocean Optics Ocean NR uncertainty of responsivity. * Except in atmospheric bands.

Spectral range	Expanded uncertainty
900 nm – 1700 nm	1,5% *

7 Characterization and calibration of spectroradiometers at NPL

7.1 Spectroradiometer instruments calibrated

Two spectroradiometers were characterised and calibrated at NPL, both were manufactured by Spectra Vista Corporation (SVC) and have HR-1024i model numbers, however the instruments have different optics configurations as shown in Table 13. The spectroradiometer SN: A222139 was owned by NPL while the spectroradiometer SN: 5192098 was supplied by the Field Spectroscopy Facility (FSF) of the National Centre for Earth Observation, University of Edinburgh, UK.

Table 13: Spectroradiometer instruments characterised at NPL

Instrument	SVC HR-1024i (SN: A222139) 		
	Manufacturer	Spectra Vista Corporation	Spectra Vista Corporation
Spectral range	337 nm – 2516 nm		340 nm – 2515 nm
Collection optics	Lens + integrating sphere with 25 mm diameter entrance aperture		Fibre bundle + integrating sphere with 25 mm diameter entrance aperture
Detector arrays	VNIR (337 nm – 1013 nm, TE-cooled) SWIR-1 (970 nm – 1909 nm, TE-cooled) SWIR-2 (1898 nm – 2516 nm, TE-cooled)		VNIR (340 nm – 1012 nm) SWIR-1 (971 nm – 1909 nm, TE-cooled) SWIR-2 (1896 nm – 2515 nm, TE-cooled)
Number of pixels	VNIR: 512 SWIR-1: 256 SWIR-2: 256		
Bandpass	VNIR: 3.3 nm SWIR-1: 9.5 nm SWIR-2: 6.5 nm		
Interface	USB connection + SVC HR-1024i software v1.24.5		

The spectroradiometers recorded the instruments' dark signal by closing an internal shutter. Each spectrum measurement with the spectroradiometer was immediately followed by a dark signal spectrum. The dark-signal subtracted spectrum in digital numbers (counts) was saved by the SVC HR-1024i software on the connected PC.

7.2 Calibration setups and standards used

7.2.1 Pixel-wavelength calibration

The pixel-wavelength assignment was determined with three spectral line lamps: Oriel Instruments Pen Ray light sources Hg, Kr, and Ar. The lamps are positioned directly in front of the entrance aperture of each

spectroradiometer. The wavelength references of the recorded emission lines were taken from the NIST atomic spectra database [12].

7.2.2 Linearity characterization

The linearity of the spectroradiometers response was characterized as a function of the detector array's integration time. The spectroradiometer signal is recorded at different integration times while measuring the irradiance from the output port of a broadband integrating sphere light source. This setup evaluates the instrument response linearity at a constant irradiance level. Linearity characterizations as a function of incident flux (irradiance levels), would require, for instance, a beam-addition setup as discussed in section 6.2.2, but the relevant NPL facility was not available at the time of this investigation.

7.2.3 Responsivity calibration

The spectral irradiance responsivity was calibrated with Gigahertz-Optik 1 kW FEL standard lamps at a 0.5 m distance from the spectroradiometer aperture opening. These FEL lamps were calibrated against a radiometrically-calibrated blackbody using the NPL Spectral Radiance and Irradiance Primary Spectroradiometer (SRIPS) facility, providing traceability to the NPL Absolute Spectral Irradiance Scale [13][12].

7.3 Characterization methods, approaches

7.3.1 Pixel-wavelength calibration

The pixel-wavelength assignment was determined from the average of 20 repeated spectra recorded for each spectral line lamp. A selection of the atomic emission lines was made based on the amplitude and location with respect to other nearby emission lines in the recorded spectra. The response of these lines was fitted with a Gaussian function to determine the location of each spectral line on the pixel array. An example of this fit is shown in Figure 48 for two Hg emission lines for the VNIR array.

Figure 48: [SVC HR-1024i] Wavelength characterisation measurement of emission lines from a Hg lamp recorded with an SVC spectroradiometer. The location on the pixel array (channel number) of two reference emission lines is found from the centre of symmetric Gaussian fits, indicated by the “Chn” fit parameter with standard uncertainties in brackets.

The fit results from the emission line measurements of the multiple spectral line lamps were combined to determine the pixel-wavelength relation. This relation was found for the separate detector arrays via fitting a polynomial function to the measured wavelengths. The order of the polynomial function was chosen as quadratic for the SWIR arrays and cubic for the VNIR array, as these were found to result in the best fits based on the number of distinct emission lines measured by each detector array and their fit residuals.

7.3.2 Linearity characterization

The deviations from linear response were determined by scaling the dark-signal subtracted signals S_c in digital numbers of pixel c with the integration times of the detector array t_{int} . The scaled signals were normalised by the signals $S_{c,ref}$ at a reference integration time $t_{int,ref}$. The deviations from a linear response were then characterised using the factor

$$\alpha_c = \frac{S_c/t_{int}}{S_{c,ref}/t_{int,ref}} - 1.$$

This non-linearity factor was plotted as a function of the spectroradiometer signal to determine the deviations from a linear response over the detector's dynamic range.

7.3.3 Responsivity calibration

The spectroradiometer responsivity R_c of each pixel number c was determined from the reference spectral irradiance of the FEL lamp source via

$$R_c = \frac{S_c}{t_{int}E_{ref}(\lambda_c)}.$$

Here S_c is the signal in digital numbers after dark signal subtraction, averaged from a series of repeated measurement, and $E_{ref}(\lambda_c)$ is the spectral irradiance of the reference light source after linear interpolation to the wavelength λ_c of the corresponding spectroradiometer pixel.

7.4 Results of characterizations

7.4.1 Pixel-wavelength calibration

The fit results of the polynomial pixel-wavelength relations are plotted in Figure 49, Figure 50, Figure 51 and Figure 52. The spectral line lamp measurements of the spectroradiometer with the fibre bundle optic (spectroradiometer SN: 5192098) resulted in only one observable emission line in the SWIR-2 array. This meant that a pixel-wavelength relation could only be determined for the VNIR and SWIR-1 arrays for this instrument.

Figure 49: [SVC HR-1024i] (SN: A222139) Dispersion functions of spectroradiometer from spectral line lamp measurements with polynomial fit functions and the uncertainties of fit parameters in brackets. The variable x is the channel number with respect to the middle channel for each detector array.

Figure 50: [SVC HR-1024i] (SN: A222139) Residuals of pixel-wavelength fit functions (crosses). The green bands show the standard uncertainty interval of the fit function. The coloured curves are the differences with respect to the manufacturer's pixel-wavelength assignment for each detector array.

Figure 51: [SVC HR-1024i] (SN: 5192098) Dispersion functions of spectroradiometer from spectral line lamp measurements for the VNIR and SWIR-1 detector arrays. The corresponding polynomial fit functions are shown with uncertainties of the fit parameters in brackets. The variable x is the channel number with respect to the middle channel for each detector array.

Figure 52: [SVC HR-1024i] (SN: 5192098) Residuals of pixel-wavelength fit functions (crosses). The green bands show the standard uncertainty interval of the fit function. The coloured curves are the differences with respect to the manufacturer's pixel-wavelength assignment for each detector array.

7.4.2 Linearity characterization

The deviations from a linear response of both spectroradiometers are plotted in Figure 53. The graphs show the individual non-linearity factors α_c plotted as a function of the dark-corrected signal S_c for each pixel within each detector array. These individual non-linearity factors have been averaged over all the pixels in each of the arrays and empirical fit functions were then determined for each array to describe the overall non-linearity characteristics; these are shown as solid black lines in the graphs. This analysis therefore assumes that the non-linearity is independent of both wavelength and irradiance, and only depends on the counts recorded by the ADC.

The non-linearity factors for the VNIR array are in the range of -1% to +1%, but increase to a range of -2% to 1.5% for signals below 3000 digital numbers. The SWIR-1 array shows non-linearities in the range of -0.5% to 1% over its dynamic range. The SWIR-2 arrays have the largest non-linearity factors and also a significant difference between the two SVC instruments. The instrument with the fibre bundle attachment (spectroradiometer SN: 5192098) exhibits about three times larger deviations from linear response in this detector array in comparison to the spectroradiometer with a lens and direct integrating sphere attachment (spectroradiometer SN: A222139). Furthermore, the different pixels in the SWIR-2 detector array of the spectroradiometer SN: 5192098 showed significant variations in non-linearities, causing the larger spread in measurements of this detector array in Figure 52. An average non-linearity relation could thus not be determined for this SWIR-2 detector array.

Figure 53: [SVC HR-1024i] Results from non-linearity characterisation measurements on SVC spectroradiometers with fit functions that show the non-linearity relation averaged over all pixels for each detector array. (Left) Instrument with lens and direct integrating sphere attachment. (Right) Instrument with integrating sphere coupled via fibre bundle attachment. An averaged non-linearity relation of the SWIR-2 detector array for the latter instrument could not be determined, due to the significant differences in non-linearity factors between the pixels.

7.4.3 Responsivity calibration

The results of the spectral irradiance responsivity calibration of the two SVC spectroradiometers are plotted in Figure 54. The responsivity of the spectroradiometer SN:5192098 was reduced in comparison to SN:A222139 due to the attenuation of the fibre bundle. The relative uncertainties in the responsivity calibration increases for both spectroradiometers near the edges of the detector array, and is generally higher for the SWIR-2 detector arrays than for the other detector arrays, since instrument noise is the dominant uncertainty contribution in this case.

Figure 54: [SVC HR-1024i] Spectral irradiance responsivities of SVC spectroradiometers from calibration on FEL lamp standards.

8 Characterization and calibration of spectroradiometers at PTB

8.1 Spectroradiometer instruments calibrated

At PTB, four array spectroradiometers manufactured by Gigahertz Optik GmbH (BTS2048) and two by Instrument Systems GmbH (CAS-140D) have been characterized and calibrated:

- **BTS2048-VL-TEC-X:** BiTec detector with cooled 2048 pixel CCD sensor and Si-photodiode with $V(\lambda)$ filter, spectral range 280 nm - 1050 nm, 1 nm bandpass, integrated filter wheel with shutter and neutral density filters, input optics for irradiance measurements (diffuser) integrated in the instrument housing,
<https://www.gigahertz-optik.com/en-us/product/bts2048-vl-tec/>
Application: transfer standard spectroradiometer, laboratory reference instrument, LED measurement, high-speed testing, goniometer measurements, candidate for A3.2.1, A3.2.3, A3.2.4
- **BTS2048-UV:** BiTec detector with cooled 2048 pixel CCD sensor and SiC photodiode, spectral range 200 nm - 430 nm, 0.8 nm bandpass, integrated filter wheel with shutter and edge filters, input optics for irradiance measurements (diffuser) integrated in the instrument housing
<https://www.gigahertz-optik.com/en-us/product/bts2048-uv/>
Application: measurement of all possible UV lamps. Due to the high stray light rejection, it is versatile in use. Laboratory reference instrument, transfer standard spectroradiometer. Candidate for A3.2.2 and A3.2.1
- **BTS2048-NIR:** BiTec detector with cooled 512 pixel array detector and InGaAs photodiode, spectral range 950 nm - 1700 nm, 5.5 nm bandpass, integrated filter wheel with shutter and neutral density filters, input optics for irradiance measurements (diffuser) integrated in the instrument housing
<https://www.gigahertz-optik.com/en-us/product/bts2048-nir/>
Application: measurement of all possible NIR LEDs. Transfer standard spectroradiometer, laboratory reference instrument. Candidate for A3.2.1, A3.2.3.
- **BTS2048-UVVISNIR:** BiTec detector with cooled 2048 pixel CCD sensor and filtered SiC photodiode, spectral range 200 nm - 900 nm, 2 nm bandpass, integrated filter wheel with shutter and edge filters, input optics for irradiance measurements (diffuser) integrated in the instrument housing
<https://www.gigahertz-optik.com/en-us/product/bts2048-uvvisnir/>
Application: multiuse device for covering various applications, especially for LEDs over a wide spectral range. Transfer standard spectroradiometer. Candidate for A3.2.1, A3.2.3, A2.3.4.
- **CAS-140D UV-VIS:** cooled, back thinned CCD area detector with 1024 x 128 pixels, spectral range 200nm – 830nm, 3.0 nm optical bandpass, integrated filter wheel with neutral density filters, input optics for irradiance measurements (diffuser head) interconnected with the instrument via a dedicated fibre bundle.
Applications: laboratory reference instrument for LED measurements, transfer standard spectroradiometer candidate for A3.2.1, A3.2.2, A3.2.3, and A3.2.4.
- **CAS-140D UV-VIS-NIR:** cooled, back thinned CCD area detector with 1024 x 128 pixels, spectral range 300nm – 1100nm, 3.7 nm optical bandpass, integrated filter wheel with neutral density filters, input optics for irradiance measurements (diffuser head) interconnected with the instrument via a dedicated fibre bundle.
Application: laboratory reference instrument for LED measurements, transfer standard spectroradiometer. Candidate for A3.2.3, and A3.2.4.

The instruments were delivered for the measurements with spectral responsivity calibrations as well as respective corrections for the radiometric nonlinearities and spectral stray light. However, since the aim of the work carried out in this activity was to characterise the spectroradiometers with respect to the relevant instrumental properties and to determine their corrections and uncertainties to be used with the digital twin model, the characterisations and calibrations of all spectroradiometers have been carried out with the manufacturer-provided corrections and calibrations turned off. Raw signals of each element of the detector arrays in digital numbers (DN), without nonlinearity or stray light corrections provided by the manufacturers, have been read out by a LabView-based software controlling the measurement setups at PTB.

8.2 Calibration setups and standards used

At PTB, a dedicated setup based on an ns-pulsed optical parametric oscillator (OPO) system of EKSPLA is available for radiometric characterizations of array spectroradiometers with respect to spectral stray light, bandpass function, and pixel-to-wavelength assignment. In addition, to complement the spectral characterization capabilities based on the narrowband spectrally tunable laser system, a new setup named “ASC” (Array Spectroradiometer Characterization) implementing simplified practical approaches for spectroradiometer characterizations has been established within the project.

8.2.1 Setup based on an ns-OPO system

The array spectroradiometer characterisation setup based on a spectrally tuneable laser system at PTB is shown schematically in Figure 8.2.1.1. The narrowband wavelength of the OPO system is automatically adjustable within spectral range from 210 nm to 2600 nm. During the measurements, the laser wavelength is monitored with an uncertainty of 10 pm using a wavemeter (laser spectrum analyser (LSA) of High Finesse) and a high-resolution spectrometer. The power of the laser beam is adjustable by a variable neutral density filter installed on a motorised rotation stage. A depolariser and a microlens array are used to homogeneously irradiate the entrance optics of a spectroradiometer. For dark signal measurements, the laser beam is automatically blocked by a shutter. The spectral characterisations are performed in a fully automated way by a LabView-based measurement control software.

Figure 8.2.1.1: Setup at PTB based on an OPO system of EKSPLA used for spectral characterisations of array spectroradiometers.

8.2.2 ASC measurement setup

The ASC facility was built to enable characterization of array spectroradiometers with respect to linearity, wavelength scale, reference plane position and spectral stray light using simplified approaches. The schematics of the ASC facility is shown in Figure 8.2.2.1.

Figure 8.2.2.1: ASC facility established at PTB within the project.

Broadband sources are essential for characterizing array spectroradiometers, providing a continuous spectrum of light that allows for comprehensive evaluation of the instrument's performance across its operational range. Various broadband light sources are selectable by a motorised translation stage No. 1: white-light LED source (S1), 150 W halogen lamp (S2), and 70 W high-pressure Xenon lamp (S3). Figure 8.2.2.2 shows exemplary signals of an array spectroradiometer measuring the broadband sources at the same distance.

Figure 8.2.2.2: Measured signal of broadband sources used in ASC facility.

An automatic shutter is installed to block the direct view of the sources and enable dark signal measurements. Two motorised filter wheels (F1 and F2) equipped with different long-pass filters shown in Table 8.2.2.1 are fixed at two positions defined by the optical axes 1 and 2.

Table 8.2.2.1: Filter wheels F1 and F2 equipped with five and eleven Schott long-pass filters.

Filter wheel F1		Filter wheel F2	
Position	Filters	Position	Filters
1	N-WG280	1	WG280
2	GG400	2	WG305
3	OG515	3	WG320
4	RG630	4	GG395
5	RG780	5	GG475
		6	OG530
		7	OG590

		8	RG665
		9	RG780
		10	RG850
		11	RG1000

The long pass colored glass filters installed in the motorised filter wheel F1 have a diameter of 25 mm while those in wheel F2 measure 12.5 mm in diameter. The plots in Figures 8.2.2.3 represent the manufacturer (Schott) nominal transmittance data of the long-pass filters. The transmittances in the blocking regions of the filters are at the level of 1e-5 or less.

Figure 8.2.2.3. Plots of manufacturer transmittance data of long-pass filters installed in F1 and F2.

For the wavelength calibration, a mercury-argon (Hg-Ar) and an Osram Cesium (Cs) pen ray lamps are used with usable spectral lines distributed throughout the spectral range from 250 nm to 1530 nm. As shown in Figure 8.2.2.1, these lamps are mounted manually for the measurements at the optical axis positions within the ASC facility. The reference emission lines are taken from the [NIST Atomic Spectra Database](#), which provides comprehensive published information on spectroscopic data for various elements. The usable wavelengths for Hg-Ar and Cs lines have been compiled in Table 8.2.2.2. Here, only the spectral lines of the elements that are more than 1 nm away from each other are listed and used for the analysis.

Table 8.2.2.2: Reference emission lines for Hg-Ar and Cs Pen lamps.

Hg I	Hg I	Ar I	Cs I	Cs I
253.6521	1367.351	763.5106	455.52799	687.04544
296.7283	1395.055	772.4207	459.31721	722.85336
334.1484	1529.582	826.4522	550.38524	727.98991
404.6565		852.1442	584.5141	794.3882
407.7837		912.2967	601.04905	801.57263
435.8335		922.4499	621.30998	807.89366
546.075		965.7786	643.19662	852.113165
579.067		1357.3617	647.26196	917.23178
1012.56		1367.855	658.60216	920.85338
1128.71			662.86576	1002.43552
1207.15			672.32838	1012.34135
1357.021			682.46513	

The translation stage 2 can hold two array spectroradiometers (DUT1 and DUT2) as well as monitor reference detectors, which allows positioning of any of those to the optical axes 1 or 2. As monitor/reference detectors, a filtered silicon detector and an extended InGaAs photodiode with limiting apertures are used for the UV-

visible and infrared ranges, respectively. The translation stage 2 is fastened to translation stage 3 with a travel range of 1.25 m. This arrangement gives an opportunity to perform measurements with any of the DUTs at various distances from the broadband light sources.

Before taking any measurements, test devices are aligned relative to the optical axis and broadband sources with the help of the alignment laser attached to the stage 1. Furthermore, the measurement plane of the test device is determined in accordance with the reference detector.

8.2.3 Spectral irradiance responsivity

The unit of spectral irradiance is realized at PTB by a blackbody-radiator of type BB3200pg. It has been characterized and optimized for the use as the national primary spectral irradiance standard. The temperature of the black-body radiator is determined with filter radiometers developed at PTB with their spectral responsivity traceable to a cryogenic radiometer as the primary standard of optical power. The spectral irradiance realized by the blackbody-radiator is transferred to secondary standards by means of a direct comparison. As secondary standards for the maintenance of the unit and customer calibrations, quartz-tungsten-halogen lamps are used in the spectral range from 250 nm to 2500 nm. In the UV spectral range from 200 nm to 400 nm, 30 W deuterium lamps are used as secondary standards.

The spectroradiometer spectral irradiance responsivity calibrations were carried out against the secondary spectral irradiance standards. A 250 W halogen (KSL) and a 30 W deuterium (DLS) lamps were used. Both secondary standard lamps have a calibration distance of 300 mm.

8.3 Characterization methods, approaches

8.3.1 Reference plane characterization

The reference plane position of the input optics of a spectroradiometer conducting spectral irradiance measurements must be known as the spectral irradiance of light sources typically varies with measurement distance from the source. The reference plane position can be determined based on the inverse square law. The characterization can additionally be supported by employing a monitor detector with a well-defined reference plane position, i.e. a mechanical aperture as a radiometric aperture stop.

In our characterization, we have designated the diffuser front surfaces of the test spectroradiometers as the reference planes and then performed irradiance measurements at varying distance from the source. The reference plane characterization in the ASC facility involved collecting both signal and dark measurements by a spectroradiometer and the monitor detector consecutively moved to the optical axis by translation stage 2. The distances were changed by translation stage 3. The collected signals as a function of distance were evaluated by the inverse square law. Specifically, the inverse of the square root of the measured signal was plotted as a function of the measurement distance. The intercept represents a distance offset between the source and the measured position of the detector.

The difference between the offset values of the spectroradiometer and the monitor detector, which reference plane is well defined, represents the offset between the front surface of the diffuser and the actual position of the reference plane. This way we have confirmed the reference plane positions of the entrance optics of the spectroradiometers with a standard uncertainty of 0.5 mm.

8.3.2 Spectral stray light

Spectral stray light defines light that reaches the detector element of an array spectroradiometer at wavelength other than intended to be measured. The fraction of the stray light-caused signal depends on both array spectroradiometer properties (scattering, interreflections, zeroth and higher diffraction orders, etc.) and the spectral power distribution of the source being measured. At PTB, the array spectroradiometers have been characterised at the tuneable laser setup in terms of line spread functions (LSFs). Furthermore, the instruments have been also characterised using a long-pass filter method at the ASC facility. Both manufacturers also provided proprietary stray light correction matrices.

8.3.2.1 Measurements of line spread functions (LSFs)

Stray light and bandpass properties of an array spectroradiometer are fully described by so-called line spread functions (LSF) that provide spectral response of the instrument to a monochromatic irradiation with a wavelength within its spectral range. Optical radiation with wavelengths outside the spectral range of the spectroradiometer but within the sensitive spectral range of the detector can cause so-called out-of-range stray light, which is to be considered by other methods, e.g. using a long-pass filter.

The LSF measurements require a spectrally pure source, which bandpass is narrower than the bandpass of a spectroradiometer under characterization. A narrowband spectrally tunable laser, like the ns-OPO system of EKSPILA, is well suitable for this purpose. Please note that the input optics of the spectroradiometer, e.g. a diffuser coupled by a fiber, may influence the stray light properties of the spectroradiometer.

The LSF measurements are carried out in two steps. For a set integration time of the spectroradiometer, e.g. 5 ms, the laser power is automatically adjusted by the NDF to reach the peak signal value of the spectroradiometer to about 50% of the maximum reachable value. Then, $N=100$ readings of dark, signal and dark again are taken. Next, the integration time is increased by a factor of 100 or more and the series of dark, signal and dark measurements is repeated. This way the dynamic range of LSF measurements is increased, yielding the LSF value over up to 6 orders of magnitude. Figure 8.3.2.1.1 shows exemplary results of such a measurement series. Combination of them yield the LSF of the array spectroradiometer at the set wavelength.

The uncertainty of the stray light correction can be basically approximated by an offset value to the stray light correction matrix representing effect of the instrument stability in the LSF measurements as discussed Schinke et al in [7].

Figure 8.3.2.1.1: Dark-corrected array spectroradiometer signals obtained with 2 ms and 400 ms integration time under laser irradiation at 500 nm.

8.3.2.2 Stray light characterization using long-pass filters

The spectral stray light is typically significantly seen in the short wavelength range, as the measured signal is typically weak here owing to the spectral power distribution of many sources and the spectral responsivity of the detector being higher at longer wavelengths as compared to shorter wavelengths. Hence, the spectral stray light-caused signal in the short visible and UV wavelength range can be estimated by using long-pass filters. As a matter of fact, the signal from the array spectroradiometer within the blocking range of the filter is caused by stray light. Therefore, the transmittances calculated from the spectroradiometer signals in spectral regions where the broadband lamp light is blocked indicate the proportion of stray light in the measurement signals.

Figure 8.3.2.2.1: Transmittances of different long-pass filters calculated from filtered halogen and Xe lamp measurements by an array spectroradiometer. The figures demonstrate that, e.g., the stray light coming from above 400 nm contributes to ca. 60% of the spectroradiometer signal at 300 nm in the case of the halogen lamp measurements and less than 3% in the case of Xe lamp measurements.

As the amount of stray light during measurements strongly depends on the light source and the spectrometer itself, we measured two broadband sources, a xenon lamp and a halogen lamp, to demonstrate the effect. The transmittance of the long-pass filters evaluated from the ratio of the measured signals of the broadband sources with filters to those with no filters in the blocking spectral regions of the filters corresponds to the fractions of the stray light signals as shown in Figure 8.3.2.2.1.

8.3.3 Linearity characterization

Nonlinearity can be observed as a function of integration time, irradiance level, ADC counts, or any combination of these factors.

The spectroradiometers under test have been measured by varying the integration time at a constant spectral irradiance. For the measurements, the xenon and halogen lamps of the ASC facility have been used. Before starting a measurement series, the integration time is chosen such that signal of 80-90% of pixels is at the saturation level. During the measurements, the integration time is gradually reduced, while at each integration time value signal and dark readings are collected. The nonlinearity for each pixel is obtained as a function of dark-corrected ADC signal. Moreover, the nonlinearities have been verified also at a fixed integration time by varying the irradiance of the lamps through distance variation and taking the ratio of the spectroradiometer signal to that of the monitor detector at every measurement distance.

8.3.4 Pixel to wavelength assignment and bandpass functions

Pixel-to-wavelength assignment is obtained from the LSF measurements at the ns-OPO-based setup. The LSFs are measured at laser wavelengths throughout the spectral range of array spectroradiometer, typically every 10 nm or even with a smaller wavelength step, if needed. The laser wavelengths are monitored by the LSA with an uncertainty of 5 pm, which allows accurately mapping pixel-to-wavelength assignment of array spectroradiometers. For every measured LSF at a set laser wavelength, the centroid pixel value is determined and assigned to the value measured by the LSA.

Note that the choice of the method for the peak pixel assignment affects the wavelength calibration of spectroradiometers, especially in the case of non-symmetrical bandpass functions, which are typical for array spectroradiometers. Therefore, it is recommended to use the centroid values of the spectral peaks rather than the maximum of the peak values for the assignment of the peaks [1], [2]. The centroid of the bandpass function in pixel space is given as a ratio of two sums,

$$Peak_c = \frac{\sum_{i=1B} i \cdot LSF(i)}{\sum_{i=1B} LSF(i)}. \quad (8.3.4.1)$$

As array spectroradiometers typically have non-symmetrical bandpass functions and are affected by near-field stray light, the centroid values may be noticeably dependent on the choice of the lower and the upper limits for summing the values in equation 8.3.4.1.

For a perfect spectrometer, a pixel-to-wavelength assignment can be approximated by a simple function, e.g. a second-order polynomial. In practice, it is not only the dispersion function of the grating spectrometer, which affects this function. It is affected also by other features of the spectrometer design, such as the focal plane

imaging and optical aberrations. Sometimes bandpass functions of the spectrometer in certain narrow spectral ranges, e.g. corresponding to the edge region of an order-sorting filter, are locally distorted. Side peaks may appear close to the main peak, or the symmetry of the peak changes abruptly, which affects the centroid values of the bandpass function as can be seen in Figure 8.3.4.1. As a result, accurate pixel-to-wavelength assignment requires characterisations on a narrow wavelength grid and choosing a higher order polynomial to parametrise the pixel-to-wavelength assignment.

Figure 8.3.4.1: variation of the LSFs of an array spectroradiometer with wavelength in the bandpass region. Note the sudden change of the function shape at 325 nm.

8.3.5 Wavelength verification at the ASC facility

At the ASC facility, the wavelength scale of an array spectroradiometer is verified against known wavelengths of atomic emission lines. Here, it is important to select for the evaluation only such emission lines, which have no neighboring lines within the bandpass of the spectroradiometer. Table 8.2.2.3 shows such lines of Hg-Ar and Cs lamps for 1 nm bandpass. Then, a series of signal and dark measurements at different integration time are made to achieve a good signal for each peak of interest, leading to a centroid wavelength of the peak.

8.3.6 Spectral irradiance responsivity calibration

The calibration of spectroradiometers with respect to the spectral irradiance responsivity was carried out by measuring the secondary spectral irradiance standard lamps under their specified geometric and electrical operating conditions, i.e. at the specified distance between the standard lamp and the reference plane of the spectroradiometer input optics, and at the operating current of the lamp. An auxiliary measurement was carried out by blocking the direct view of the lamp while letting the entrance optics of the spectroradiometer see the rest of the room. This signal accounts for the dark signal of the instrument and the spatial stray light. For spectroradiometers with the upper wavelength of their spectral range well below 1100 nm, e.g. 830 nm, additional measurements were carried out by using long-pass filters with the cut-on wavelength matching the edge of the spectral range to account for the out-of-range stray light. By subtracting this signal, both the out-of-range stray light and the above-mentioned spatial stray light and the dark signal are taken into account. The spectral irradiance responsivity of the array spectroradiometer $S_{E,i}$ of pixel i is obtained then as

$$S_{E,i} = \frac{y_{S,i} - y_{OoR,S,i} / T_{OoR}}{E_{\lambda,S}(\lambda_i)} \prod_{j=1}^n f_{S,j}(\lambda_i), \quad (8.3.6.1)$$

where:

$y_{S,i}$ – dark-corrected signal of pixel i and measurement of the calibration source S ,

$y_{OoR,S,i}$ – dark-corrected signal of pixel i caused by the out-of-range (OoR) stray light during the measurement of the source S ,

T_{OoR} – passband transmittance of the long-pass filter used for the OoR measurement,

$E_{\lambda,S}(\lambda_i)$ – spectral irradiance of the calibration source S ,

$f_{S,j}(\lambda_i)$ – wavelength-dependent correction factor (linearity, wavelength, distance, stray light, etc) for measurement of the calibration source S .

8.4 Results of characterizations: determined corrections

8.4.1 Results of stray light characterization

The measurements at the ns-OPO setup yielded LSFs of the array spectroradiometers, shown in Figure 8.4.1.1. Note that the selection of the laser wavelengths for the LSF measurements of each instrument was based on the spectral shape and variation with excitation wavelength of the LSFs. In case the instrument showed various features in their LSFs which also vary with the excitation wavelength, the grid of the measurement wavelengths was adjusted accordingly to avoid interpolation errors of the LSFs while establishing the stray light correction matrix.

Figure 8.4.1.1a: measured LSFs of BTS2048-VL-TEC-X.

Figure 8.4.1.1b: measured LSFs of BTS2048-UV.

Figure 8.4.1.1c: measured LSFs of BTS2048-NIR.

Figure 8.4.1.1d: measured LSFs of BTS2048-UVVISNIR.

Figure 8.4.1.1e: measured LSFs of CAS-140D UV-VIS.

Figure 8.4.1.1f: measured LSFs of CAS-140D UV-VIS-NIR.

The measured LSFs were interpolated to obtain an LSF for every pixel of the array detector. The interpolated LSFs were then processed to stray light correction matrices according to Zong et al. Figure 8.4.1.2 shows an exemplary one such a matrix, for BTS2048-VL-TEC-X.

Figure 8.4.1.2: Stray light correction matrix D for BTS2048-VL-TEC-X.

8.4.2 Stray light correction using long-pass filters

The amount of spectral stray light in spectroradiometer signal can be determined by using long-pass filters, as discussed in section 8.3.2.2. To estimate the stray light at UV and short VIS wavelengths, the correction method by Ma et al [3], [4] can be used. We have implemented the “weighted long pass filter method” which involves employing various long-pass filters within the spectral range of spectroradiometer.

A spectroradiometer’s complete spectral range can be divided into multiple subranges, determined by the cut-on wavelengths of the long-pass filters used. Subsequently, the stray light factor (Stf) for a specific long-pass filter can be computed by weighing the measured filtered signal in the blocking range of filter against the integral of the filtered signal in the pass band, as illustrated in equation below:

$$Stf(\lambda) = \frac{S_f(\lambda)}{\int_{\lambda_c}^{\lambda_{end}} S_f(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad (8.4.2.1)$$

The calculated stray light factors from all subranges are combined in equation 8.4.2.2 to correct the measured signal for stray light.

Further, the corrected signal for a test source can be determined by utilizing the measured signal at longer wavelengths and the evaluated stray light factors for the calibration source, as expressed in the following equation:

$$S_{corr}(\lambda) = S_{nf}(\lambda) - Stf(\lambda)[calibration\ source] \int_{\lambda_c}^{\lambda_{end}} S_{nf}(\lambda)[test\ source] d\lambda \quad (8.4.2.2)$$

Here, $\lambda \geq \lambda_c$; λ_c = cut on wavelength of long-pass filter,
 $S_{corr}(\lambda)$: stray light-corrected signal,
 S_{nf} : measured signal with no filter,
 S_f : measured signal with filter,
 λ_{end} : end wavelength of spectral range of spectroradiometer.

The cut on wavelength of long-pass filter is the wavelength that corresponds to the lowest transmittance just before the gradual transition to the pass band.

BTS2048-VL-TEC-X, BTS2048-UVVISNIR, CAS-140D UV-VIS and CAS-140D UV-VIS-NIR were characterised this way. Please note that the weighted filter method does not account for the out-of-range stray light. Figure 8.4.2.1 shows the calculated transmittance of the long-pass filters evaluated from the measured signals in the case of filtered xenon and halogen lamps.

Figure 8.4.2.1: Transmittances of different long-pass filters calculated from filtered halogen and Xe lamp measurements by BTS2048-VL-TEC-X and CAS140D-UUVISNIR.

A disparity in the fraction of the stray light-caused signals can be seen for the two sources, xenon and halogen lamps. Stray light-caused signal at 300 nm accounts to 30%-60% for the halogen lamp measurements by the two instruments while for the xenon lamp it varies between 3% to 1%.

Figure 8.4.2.2 compares results of the stray light correction in the UV - short VIS range assuming the halogen lamp is used as a calibration source and the xenon lamp as test source. Red lines are obtained from the measurement data using the above equations. The yellow line is the result of the stray light correction matrices (SCM) applied to both lamp measurements.

Figure 8.4.2.2: Stray light correction (%) in the UV region for BTS2048-VL-TEC-X and CAS140D-UUVISNIR evaluated from weighted long-pass filter and SCM method. For both instruments, the stray light-caused errors are effectively corrected.

The graph shows that notable stray light-caused errors would be caused in the irradiance measurements, especially for wavelengths under 400 nm, if no corrections were applied. The stray light corrections reduce stray light signals by up to a factor of 100. The figure also demonstrates the constraints of the weighted long-

pass filter method, particularly at the filter edges, where slight discrepancies are observed due to the cut-on wavelength of the filter.

8.4.3 Linearity characterization

All six spectroradiometers have been characterized for nonlinearity by varying the integration time. Both Xe and halogen lamps were used for the measurements. During the characterizations, the nonlinearity correction functions of the manufacturers were deactivated. Figure 8.4.3.1 shows exemplary results of such measurements for the BTS2048-VL-TEC-X and for the CAS140D-UVVISNIR. The integration time has been varied from 100 ms to 30 s and from 4 ms to 330 ms for both instruments, respectively.

Figure 8.4.3.1: Results of nonlinearity characterization as a function of dark subtracted counts measured at different integration times of two spectroradiometers, (a) from GGO, and (b) from IS. The colored dots represent the pixel-wise nonlinearity. The red lines correspond to the 2nd order and 6th degree polynomial fitted to these data points to correct for the nonlinearity.

The deviations from the linearity as a function of dark-subtracted ADC counts have been fitted by polynomials, which are shown in Figure 8.4.3.2.

Figure 8.4.3.2: Polynomials determined for the six characterized spectroradiometers.

8.4.4 Pixel-to-wavelength assignment

For pixel-to-wavelength assignment of the array spectroradiometers, the measured LSFs of the instruments and the associated laser wavelengths, monitored by the LSA at the EKSPILA setup were used. The peak pixel positions of the LSFs were calculated as centroid value of the LSF peak. The obtained set of a

spectroradiometer pixels and corresponding wavelengths was fitted by a polynomial. Figure 8.4.4.1 shows the results of the calibration.

Figure 8.4.4.1a: BTS2048-VL-TEC-X: measured peak pixels (centroid over $\pm 1FWHM$) corresponding to set laser wavelengths, 8th-order polynomial fit and the residuals (left figure); deviation between the determined wavelengths and the nominal wavelengths of all pixels (right figure).

Figure 8.4.4.1b: BTS2048-UV: measured peak pixels (centroid over $\pm 1FWHM$) corresponding to set laser wavelengths, 5th-order polynomial fit and the residuals (left figure); deviation between the determined wavelengths and the nominal wavelengths of all pixels (right figure).

Figure 8.4.4.1c: BTS2048-NIR: measured peak pixels (centroid over $\pm 1FWHM$) corresponding to set laser wavelengths, 3rd-order polynomial fit and the residuals (left figure); deviation between the determined wavelengths and the nominal wavelengths of all pixels (right figure).

Figure 8.4.4.1d: BTS2048-UVVISNIR: measured peak pixels (centroid over $\pm 1FWHM$) corresponding to set laser wavelengths, 7th-order polynomial fit and the residuals (left figure); deviation between the determined wavelengths and the nominal wavelengths of all pixels (right figure).

Figure 8.4.4.1e: CAS-140D UV-VIS: measured peak pixels (centroid over $\pm 1FWHM$) corresponding to set laser wavelengths, 4th-order polynomial fit and the residuals (left figure); deviation between the determined wavelengths and the nominal wavelengths of all pixels (right figure).

Figure 8.4.4.1f: CAS-140D UV-VIS-NIR: measured peak pixels (centroid over $\pm 1FWHM$) corresponding to set laser wavelengths, 3rd-order polynomial fit and the residuals (left figure); deviation between the determined wavelengths and the nominal wavelengths of all pixels (right figure).

8.4.5 Wavelength verification at the ASC facility

By utilizing the emission lines of the Hg-Ar and the Cs pen lamps, we have verified the wavelength scales of the array spectroradiometers. The measured peak wavelengths, calculated as centroids over $\pm 1FWHM$ from the peak, have been compared to the reference line positions and the deviations are shown in Figure 8.4.5.1. The uncertainty of the peak determination was estimated from the measured bandpass function of the instruments.

Figure 8.4.5.1: Plot of wavelength deviations of the array spectroradiometers at the atomic emission lines of the pen lamps.

8.4.6 Bandpass functions

Bandpass functions of array spectroradiometers have been obtained from the measured LSFs. The LSFs of the six array spectroradiometers measured at PTB are shown in chapter 8.4.1. The bandpass of a spectrometer is typically described by a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the bandpass function. The FWHM as a function of wavelength is shown for the six spectroradiometers in Figure 8.4.6.1. Note that bandpass correction methods use bandpass values, which are obtained by normalising spectral integral values of the function to their maximum values.

Figure 8.4.6.1: Variation of the FWHM throughout the spectral ranges of the characterised array spectroradiometers.

8.4.7 Spectral irradiance responsivity

The spectroradiometers of both manufacturers were calibrated with respect to their spectral irradiance responsivities. During the calibration, no manufacturer-provided corrections for nonlinearity, stray light etc. were used. Only the above discussed characterization results obtained at PTB were employed in the spectral correction functions according to equation 8.3.6.1.

Measured spectral irradiance responsivities of the array spectroradiometers together with the associated uncertainties are presented in Figure 8.4.7.1. For the instrument calibrations, a halogen lamp as a secondary spectral irradiance standard was used. The response of the spectroradiometers is expressed in digital numbers (DN) normalized by the integration time. The determined stray light correction matrices were applied to the signals of the instruments. For the BTS2048-UV and CAS-140D UV-VIS, also the out-of-range signals were subtracted, which were measured with the long-pass filters with the cut-off wavelengths at 400 nm and 830 nm, respectively. In the middle of the spectral ranges of the instruments, the calibration uncertainty was dominated

by the uncertainty of the secondary spectral irradiance standard and the position uncertainty of the reference plane. The spectral stray light causes dominant uncertainty contribution at the edges of the spectral ranges.

Figure 8.4.7.1: Spectral irradiance responsivity (black curve, left axis) and uncertainty components of the measurements (coloured curves, right axis).

A deuterium secondary standard lamp (DLS) was used to verify irradiance responsivity calibrations of the spectroradiometers in the UV spectral range, where the spectral ranges of both standard lamps overlap. Large discrepancies between the calibration results would be seen in case the spectral stray light correction is missing or not effective. Figure 8.4.7.2 shows the spectral irradiance responsivities retrieved both from the halogen (KSL) and the deuterium (DLS) secondary standards. The determined responsivities agree well within associated uncertainties.

Figure 8.4.7.2: Spectral irradiance responsivity determined from the measurements of the halogen (KSL) and the deuterium (DLS) standard lamps.

9 Characterization and calibration of spectroradiometers at RISE

9.1 Spectroradiometer instruments calibrated

The calibrated and characterized device is a spectrometer in the VIS range, which, according to the manufacturer, is an easy-to-use device suited for testing light sources, screens, and room illuminance/luminance. The device was provided by a stakeholder of the NEWSTAND project.

According to a sticker on the spectrometer, it was calibrated by the manufacturer in 2017 with NIST traceability. The device automatically detects the fitted optics, applies the calibration, and presents the results as radiance or irradiance, depending on the optics. Accessing the calibration menu requires a password, which was unknown, so all evaluations were performed with the stored calibration setting. Additionally, the raw detector signal (number of counts) cannot be exported but only viewed in the software. Thus, all analysis was done on data with the stored calibration already applied and interpolated by the software to a 1 nm interval in the range of 380 to 780 nm. The spectrometer has a built-in shutter and, by default, measures and corrects each measurement for the dark signal.

Instrument	<p style="text-align: center;">Jeti Specbos 1201 (s/n 3172065)</p>	
Manufacturer	JETI Technische Instrumente GmbH	
Spectral range (nm)	380-780	
Spectral bandwidth, FWHM (nm)	5	
Number of pixels	512	
Irradiance optics	Diffuser cap	
Radiance optics	1.8° viewing angle (default) 1.9° ø1 mm @ 26 mm (with focusing optics)	
Resolution ADC	16 bit (15 bit used, 14 bit displayed)	
Integration time range	1 ms to 60 s	
Size (mm)	150 x 58 x 34	
Weight (g)	300	
Operating ambient temperature range (°C)	10 to 40	
Software interface	USB 2.0	
Software	JETI LiVal V8.0.3	

9.2 Calibration setups and standards used

Calibration of the spectral irradiance and the wavelength scale of the spectrometer was carried out in the Photometry & Radiometry laboratory at RISE, with the temperature controlled to $23 \pm 1^\circ$.

For spectral irradiance, the spectrometer was fitted with the diffuser cap and calibrated against one of RISE's spectral irradiance standards (1000 W FEL, no. F-672) with traceability to NIST, USA. The calibration was carried out at 50,0 cm from the lamp.

The wavelength scale of the spectrometer was calibrated with Oriel Spectral Line lamps (Hg, Ne and Kr), utilizing suitable lines in the range of 380-780 nm. Additionally, a HeNe laser at 633 nm was used.

9.3 Characterization methods, approaches

RISE's standard method for calibrating spectral irradiance was used to check the spectrometer's stored calibration data. The spectrometer was fitted with the diffuser cap and calibrated against one of RISE's spectral irradiance standards (1000 W FEL, no. F-672) with traceability to NIST, USA. The calibration was carried out at 50,0 cm from the lamp. In addition, repeatability measurements were performed using the same lamp.

The wavelength scale of the spectrometer was calibrated with Oriel Spectral Line lamps (Hg, Ne and Kr), utilizing suitable lines in the range of 380-780 nm. Additionally, a HeNe laser at 633 nm was used. Around each line, the captured data was interpolated from 1 nm to 0,1 nm using a cubic spline, and then the center wavelength was determined based on the 50% levels of the peak. These measurements were also used to determine the FWHM bandwidth of the spectrometer.

The linearity of the spectrometer was characterized for different integration times (10 ms to 60 s) as well as for different irradiance levels (no. of counts). Two different setups were used to determine the linearity with respect to the integration time. The first setup utilized a commercial sphere-based luminance halogen source where the luminance can be changed between 0 and about 50000 cd/m^2 by adjusting a slit between the halogen lamp and the sphere. The output luminance is monitored with a photometric detector, whose linearity has been verified over the full range. As adjusting the luminance level also changes the relative spectral radiance to some extent, the analysis of linearity was performed using photometric values. By varying the luminance from about 50 to 50000 cd/m^2 integration times between 10 ms and 10 s were covered. The second setup utilizes a power-stabilized Nd:YAG laser at 532 nm fed into an integrating sphere. Using an optical wedge, a small part of the beam was used to determine the reference level with a linear trap detector. The setup is shown in Figure 9.3.1 below. Additionally, neutral density filters were used to increase the dynamic range allowing for integration times from 100 ms to 60 s to be included. These evaluations were performed using the automatic integration time setting in the spectrometer which normally resulted in a signal level of approximately 80% of saturation.

Figure 9.3.1: Linearity setup with an Nd:YAG laser at 532 nm (right) illuminating an integrating sphere (left).

The non-linearity with constant irradiance and different integration times was determined using a 1000 W FEL lamp. The spectrometer was kept at a fixed distance from the lamp, and the integration time was changed to cover the full range of the spectrometer, i.e., the number of counts.

A simplified investigation of stray light levels was performed using several narrow laser lines and a set of long pass filters. The principles behind these methods are described elsewhere in this report. Given the spectral range of the Jeti spectrometer (VIS) and the relatively limited resolution (14 bit), the obtained irradiance curves have only been used for a qualitative assessment of the stray light levels.

The position of the entrance plane relative to the front of the spectrometer's diffusor cap was determined by measuring the spectral irradiance from a 1000 W FEL lamp at distances between 500 mm and 1750 mm in 250 mm steps. The entrance plane was determined by using the inverse square law while accounting for the lamp's offset from the reference plane. The nonlinearity of the spectrometer was compensated for based on the linearity measurement.

9.4 Results of characterizations

9.4.1 Spectral irradiance calibration

The results for the spectral irradiance calibration with the stored calibration file applied are shown in Figure 9.4.1.1. For the shorter wavelength the results are dominated by noise, but for the main part of the spectrum the deviations are less than 2% from the reference values. This is also in line with the estimated uncertainty for the spectral irradiance of the standard lamp.

Figure 9.4.1.1: Measured spectral irradiance with the Jeti Specbos and the deviation from reference values.

The overall repeatability of ten single measurements taken using the same spectral irradiance lamp is shown in Figure 9.4.1.2. The standard uncertainty is about 5% at 380 nm, quickly decreasing to below 1% at 420 nm and below 0,2% at 500 nm.

Figure 9.4.1.2: Repeatability, 10 single measurements of spectral irradiance.

9.4.2 Wavelength calibration and bandwidth

The results for the wavelength calibration and the evaluation of the spectrometer's bandwidth are presented in Tables 9.4.2.1 and 9.4.2.2 below. Since the spectrometer has a limited wavelengths resolution (512 pixels interpolated to whole nm in the result output), all values have been rounded to 0,1 nm. Note that except for the HeNe-laser, which has a known wavelength, the other laser lines (semiconductor laser at 405 nm and a Ti:Sapphire laser system for 550 and 770 nm) have only been used to determine the bandwidth and not the wavelength deviation.

Table 9.4.2.1: Wavelength calibration and determination of spectrometer bandwidth using Oriol spectral line lamps.

Lamp	Reference wavelength	Measure wavelength	Deviation	Bandwidth (FWHM)
	[nm]	[nm]	[nm]	[nm]
Hg	404.7	404.1	-0.6	5.0
Hg	435.8	435.2	-0.6	4.4
Hg	546.1	545.7	-0.4	4.3
Ne	659.9	659.7	-0.2	4.6
Ne	693.0	692.8	-0.2	4.5
Ne	724.5	724.3	-0.2	4.4
Kr	587.1	586.8	-0.3	4.4

Table 9.4.2.2: Wavelength calibration and determination of spectrometer bandwidth using laser lines.

Laser	Reference wavelength	Measure wavelength	Deviation	Bandwidth (FWHM)
	[nm]	[nm]	[nm]	[nm]
405 nm	-	-	-	4.6
Red HeNe	632.8	632.5	-0.3	4.5
550 nm	-	-	-	4.4
770 nm	-	-	-	4.5

Figure 9.4.2.1: Summary of the measured wavelength deviations.

9.4.3 Linearity

The results for the linearity measurements are presented in Figures 9.4.3.1 and 9.4.3.2 below. Disregarding very short integration times and very low signals, the linearity of the spectrometer is within 1% both for the integration time and for the signal level (number of counts). Also, no significant spectral dependence for linearity can be seen (Figure 9.4.3.2).

Figure 9.4.3.1. Linearity of the spectrometer with respect to different integration times, normalized to 100 ms. Different luminance/radiance and automatic integration time setting.

Figure 9.4.3.2. Linearity of the spectrometer with respect to the number of counts, normalized to 95%. Integration times from 1 ms to 40 ms, diffuser cap with constant irradiance level.

9.4.4 Stray light

The results for the simplified stray light evaluations are presented in Figures 9.4.4.1 and 9.4.4.2 below. From the graphs it can be concluded that the stray light increases at shorter wavelengths as expected and has some significance in comparison to the noise floor in the whole wavelength range of the spectrometer. However, except for in the shortest wavelength range, the possible influence of stray light is well below 1% and can therefore most likely be ignored in most situations.

Figure 9.4.4.1. Measured LSFs with four narrow laser lines.

Figure 9.4.4.2. Measured spectral transmittance for long pass filters using the Jeti Specbos and a halogen lamp.

9.4.5 Diffusor entrance plane

By minimizing the deviations from the inverse square law, the offset of the entrance plane was determined to -1.22 mm relative to the front of the diffusor. However, even without no offset the deviations are smaller than the estimated uncertainty (due to distance, repeatability, non-linearity etc.) and the offset value can therefore not be considered significant. The measured deviations when comparing the measured integrated irradiance values with the theoretical values determined by the inverse square law is presented in Figure 9.4.5.1.

Figure 9.4.5.1. Deviations between measured and theoretical values, without and with offset.

10 Characterization and calibration of spectroradiometers at TUBITAK

10.1 Spectroradiometer instruments calibrated

The spectrometer Avantes AvaSpec-mini2048L has a spectral range of 220 nm to 1100 nm and features a CCD linear photodiode array (2048 pixels), a symmetric Czerny-Turner design with a 75 mm focal length, a signal-to-noise ratio of 300:1, and a 16-bit ADC converter. It utilizes a fiber optic cable with a cosine-corrected diffuser at the input optics and operates via a USB 2.0 interface.

End-user applications: colorimetry, lighting technology

10.2 Calibration setups and standards used

10.2.1 Calibration Standards

For spectral responsivity, 1000 W FEL type lamp with GIGAHERTZ OPTIC BN-9101 is used as Spectral Irradiance transfer standard lamp.

For wavelength calibration, Low Pressure Light Sources with Ocean Optics Hg(Ar) are used as a reference standard lamps.

For nonlinearity characterization as a function of the integration time, a stable 1000 W FEL type irradiance light source is used.

10.3 Characterization methods, approaches

10.3.1 Nonlinearity

Nonlinearity of the spectrometer as a function of integration time at constant signal level is measured using a stable irradiance light source. A saturated signal is obtained at a fixed distance from the spectrometer. Then decreasing the integration time, measurements are performed at several different integration times. At each integration time, the dark measurements are performed and subtracted from the signal measurements

10.3.2 Spectral scale

The wavelength calibration of the spectrometer is performed using Low Pressure Light Sources. The signals of Low Pressure Light Sources and associated dark signals are measured and dark signals are subtracted from the related main signals. The peak values of the measured signal were calculated as centroid wavelengths and compared to Low Pressure Light Sources theoretical values. A fitting function is obtained using the measured and theoretical values and the fitting function is used to correct the wavelength of readings.

10.3.3 Responsivity

The spectral irradiance level sensitivity calibration is performed using a 1000 W FEL-type reference irradiance lamp in the irradiance measurement setup established on an optical table. The distance between the calibrated spectrometer with a cosine-corrected diffuser and the spectral irradiance standard lamp is set to 70 cm. After the current supplied to the reference irradiance light source reaches stability, measurements are carried out using the spectrometer software.

10.4 Results of characterization

10.4.1 Nonlinearity Results

Measurement results are normalized using the integration times and normalized the values using reference value to one. A fitting function is derived from the graph of the normalized results in order to correct the nonlinearity of measurements.

The regression (7th degree polynomial fitting) results of Avantes Mini Spectrometer:

Coefficients	Values
Intercept	0,96667
1 st coefficient	-3,61e-06
2 nd coefficient	1,50e-09
3 rd coefficient	-1,46e-13
4 th coefficient	6,88e-18
5 th coefficient	-1,68e-22

6 th coefficient	2,06e-27
7 th coefficient	-9,93e-33

10.4.2 Avantes AvaSpec-mini2048L Wavelength Results

Reference Peak Wavelength (nm)*	Peak Wavelength (nm)	Error (nm)
365,02	365,04	0,02
404,66	404,62	-0,04
435,83	435,80	-0,03
546,07	546,12	0,05
696,54	696,54	0,00
727,29	727,27	-0,02
738,4	738,37	-0,03
763,51	763,49	-0,02
772,42	772,39	-0,03
794,82	794,8	-0,02
826,45	826,46	0,01
852,14	852,20	0,06

* Low Pressure Light Sources were used

10.4.3 Avantes AvaSpec-mini2048L Irradiance responsivity results

Spectral Range	Expanded Uncertainty of Irradiance Responsivity
340 nm - 400 nm	4.5%
400 nm - 900 nm	3.5%

11 Characterization and calibration of spectroradiometers at VSL

11.1 Spectroradiometer instruments calibrated

Two of the same models of spectroradiometers provided to VSL by Avantes for this project were characterized. These spectroradiometers are two copies of a newer model built by Avantes with the aim of reproducibility over time. These two instruments were read out using the most up to date SDK provided by Avantes and the raw measurement data was in 16-bit binary counts from the ADC at each of the 2048 pixel positions. All corrections installed by Avantes in the on-board memory of the instrument as delivered to VSL were removed or disabled prior to characterization measurements in this chapter.

Manufacturer	Avantes
Model	VARIUS, AvaSpec-VRS2048CL-EVO
Serial number(s)	7415925SP, 7415927SP
Link to datasheet	https://www.avantes.com/content/uploads/2024/02/Tech-data-Varius-v4-07-02.pdf
Spectral range (nm)	190 - 1100
Spectral bandwidth, FWHM (nm)	1.5 - 2.3
Spectral sampling interval (nm/pixel)	0.42 - 0.49
Number of channels	2048
Irradiance optics	5 cm Integrating sphere, fiber coupled
Radiance optics	No
Resolution ADC	16 bit
Minimum integration / exposure time (µs)	9
Electrical power consumption (W)	3.6
Size (cm x cm x cm)	18.3 x 13 x 4.52
Mass (kg)	1.068
Temperature stabilisation	No
Operating ambient temperature range (°C)	5 - 55
Control interface	USB 3.0/Ethernet
Software interface	SDK and commercial software
Output data format	ASCII, Excel
End-user applications	Lighting, Laboratory irradiance/radiance, semiconductor, agriculture & food, system integration

11.2 Calibration setups and standards used

The measurements presented in the following sections were carried out at an ambient temperature of (23.0 ± 0.5) °C and a relative air humidity of (45 ± 10) %.

11.2.1 Wavelength-pixel relation

For spectral line calibration, five atomic emission sources were utilized: cesium (Cs), argon (Ar), helium (He), cadmium (Cd), and mercury-argon (HgAr). A total of 35 spectral lines were observed across the wavelength range of 248.266 nm to 1012.357 nm, as shown in Table 14. The wavelength positions of the pixels were determined using these spectral line sources. Three low-pressure gas discharge lamps from Osram (Cs, He, and Cd) were used, with each lamp given more than 30 minutes of stabilization time after startup. Additionally, two pen lamps from Newport, containing Ar gas (model 6030) and Ar gas and Hg vapor (model 6035), were used after a similar stabilization period. The closely spaced literature wavelengths in air from the NIST database [12] were weighted and used for the spectral line calibration as reference values when observing the different spectral lamps mentioned.

The entrance optics of the spectroradiometer were directly illuminated with these emission sources without any intermediate optical elements. Each lamp spectrum was recorded 100 times using the two Varius spectroradiometers, while the integration time for the measurements varied between 45 ms and 1400 ms. Afterwards each spectrum was corrected for the dark taken immediately following each measurement. This range of integration times was necessary in order to observe relatively weak spectral lines. However, for the longest integration times, the most intense spectral lines saturated the detector, and such saturated regions of the spectra recorded were excluded from further analysis.

Table 14: The weighted central wavelengths of the spectral lines observed using five atomic emission sources, cesium (Cs), argon (Ar), helium (He), cadmium (Cd), and mercury-argon (HgAr).

Reference wavelength (nm)	Emission line source	Reference wavelength (nm)	Emission line source	Reference wavelength (nm)	Emission line source
248.266	Hg	546.075	Hg	763.511	Ar
253.652	Hg	587.568	He	794.818	Ar
296.728	Hg	601.049	Cs	826.452	Ar
326.105	Cd	621.385	Cs	852.144	Ar
346.685	Cd	643.847	Cd	876.141	Cs
365.338	Hg	667.728	He	912.297	Ar
388.865	He	687.129	Cs	922.450	Ar
415.921	Ar	696.543	Ar	965.779	Ar
435.820	Hg	706.723	Ar	1002.436	Cs
455.528	Cs	714.704	Ar	1012.357	Cs
479.991	Cd	727.287	Ar		
508.582	Cd	738.375	Ar		

11.2.2 Nonlinearity

Nonlinearity calibration of Varius spectroradiometers was performed at VSL using a portable calibration setup consisting of a diode laser coupled into a 2-inch integrating sphere with 2 output ports and a variable attenuator between the laser and integrating sphere. The variable attenuator allows for the irradiance to be adjusted while simultaneous measurements from both detectors are recorded across a range of light levels. The calibration setup follows a concept derived from a portable system previously developed at VSL [5] within the EMRP project "Traceability for Surface Spectral Solar Ultraviolet Radiation" (SolarUV.) The irradiance reaches the Varius instrument and a monitor detector that serves as a linearity reference. The diode laser is first allowed to stabilize before the attenuation system is adjusted in an initial stage to provide the maximum light level suitable for the monitor detector's linear operation during further characterization.

Figure 55: Setup for measurement of the nonlinearity at fixed integration time.

Several enhancements were made to this system in this project, including replacing the variable attenuator with a combination of a half-wave plate and a linear polarizer, whose transmission axis is controlled with a rotation mount. To mitigate coherence effects of the laser in the integrating sphere, the laser beam is reflected from a rotating mirror and into the integrating sphere, ensuring uniform light distribution reaches the Avantes spectroradiometer. The monitor silicon detector (Hamamatsu S1227) is positioned at one exit port of the sphere. The setup’s flexibility allows the use of different diode lasers to assess detector performance across various spectral positions. In this project, a 670 nm diode laser (Thorlabs CPS670F) was used which produces approximately 4.5 mW at its output.

11.2.3 Spectral stray light and bandpass

VSL used a widely tuneable, pulsed laser-based setup to measure spectral stray light of the Varius spectroradiometers characterized in this project. This system at VSL [9] consists of a nanosecond pulsed laser source from the manufacturer Ekspla (NT242) utilizing an optical parametric oscillator to produce tuneable monochromatic laser light covering the ultraviolet (UV), visible (VIS), and infrared (IR) spectral regions. The laser operates with nanosecond pulse durations at a repetition rate of 1 kHz. Since the setup can produce radiation from the UV to the IR, it can accommodate a broad range of spectroradiometers, including the Varius spectroradiometers characterized in this project.

Figure 56: Improved setup for measurement of spectral straylight correction matrix based on tuneable pulsed OPO laser.

The setup allows for illuminating the spectroradiometer with monochromatic light and capturing the in-band and the out-of-band response from all detector pixels [6]. The setup is automated to introduce light at a series of wavelengths, and the resulting signals across the detector array are captured. The setup was improved in this project to automate high dynamic range measurements at three different integration times. An initial integration time of 10 ms was set as a minimum level and a maximum of several or tens of seconds was typically used. The setup has an automatic reflective ND filter wheel to adaptively attenuate the laser light to

no greater than 58,000 counts at the peak since the output energy of the laser varies with wavelength. All wavelengths were sampled 50 times in total at each integration time. Dark measurements were taken prior to and following each measurement.

Measurements were taken using this setup at more than 50 distinct wavelengths in the first of the two Varius spectroradiometers characterized spanning from 225 nm to 1111 nm. Simultaneously, the wavelength output of the Ekspla laser is observed using an LSA 2137 wavemeter from High Finesse to check picometer changes in the laser wavelength before and after each measurement. Using information from the characterization of the first instrument, it was determined that fewer wavelengths were to be measured in the characterization of the second instrument (about 35 wavelengths measured). This setup enabled the detection of out-of-band signals at levels as low as about 10^{-6} to 10^{-7} of the peak laser intensity, depending on the integration time settings as shown in the results of section 11.4.3.1.

11.2.4 Spectral irradiance responsivity

A known spectral irradiance level from a calibrated FEL lamp transfer standard source is observed with the two Varius spectroradiometers using a preset integration time optimized for signal level and averaged 100 times. This transfer standard lamp is calibrated by NIST from 250 nm to 2400 nm using NIST's FASCAL 2 facility.

11.3 Characterization methods, approaches

11.3.1 Wavelength-pixel relation

The characterization process involves determining the pixel position as the centroid [1], or weighted average, for each observed emission line and comparing it to the corresponding reference wavelengths in air. For the calculation of the centroid, only the pixel positions near each of the emission lines was included in the average, which is assumed to be the in-band counts. Each integration was therefore limited to a region of pixels or about 3 nm around each central wavelength. Using dark corrected measurements, the centroid was calculated using the formula:

$$\frac{\int IB \cdot IB_{pixels} dIB_{pixels}}{\int IB dIB_{pixels}}$$

where IB is the in-band counts at each of a set of pixel locations IB_{pixels} . Using this approach, a dataset was constructed that mapped each reference wavelength to its corresponding average pixel location on the detector array. A polynomial fit of degree 3 (and alternatively higher degrees) can be applied to establish the relationship between pixel position x and wavelength λ [1]:

$$\lambda = ax^3 + bx^2 + cx + d$$

The values of these polynomials fit to the data are found in Figure 57 and Figure 58.

11.3.2 Nonlinearity

The nonlinearity characterization of the two Avantes Varius instruments is performed by directly comparing its response to a known linear monitor detector. The irradiance was varied at a fixed integration time while monitoring both the spectroradiometer and a monitor detector [5]. The integration time is preset to ensure the maximum of the Varius instrument's ADC count is approximately 58,000 and thereafter it is kept constant. After alignment of the monitor detector and both Varius spectroradiometers, the fixed integration time determined for the measurements was 150 ms. This diode laser based variable source produced irradiance of at most about 10^1 W/m²/nm at the entrance plane of the spectroradiometer, corresponding to about 10 μ A in the monitor detector.

The irradiance is systematically adjusted using the variable attenuator in the setup, while simultaneous measurement of the monitor and spectroradiometer are recorded. This is repeated across a range of light

levels. At each light level, both light and dark measurements are acquired. That way the dark can be corrected for in all measurements using both the Varius and monitor detector before further analysis. From these corrected measurements, the deviation from linearity is simply calculated using the formula:

$$\frac{C_{DUT}/U_{ref}}{R_0}$$

where C_{DUT} is the Varius instrument's corrected reading at the wavelength (pixel) of the measurement normalized to the monitor detector's voltage signal, U_{ref} , due to its response at a specific fixed irradiance level, R_0 , which was taken around 40,000 counts.

11.3.3 Spectral stray light and bandpass

To quantify spectral stray light matrix, the Varius instrument's response to the localized, monochromatic illumination at a specific wavelengths [6] due to the tuneable laser is recorded in the detector array. The resulting signal distribution across all pixels is analyzed using a high dynamic range method [7], [8] to merge multiple measurements of three different integration times. This gives a higher dynamic range in the detection of stray light resulting from illumination at out-of-band parts of the detector array of each Varius. This merging forms the Line Spread Function (LSF). A set of LSFs is created by measuring at many wavelengths across the detector array. This is one method to characterize this type of spectral stray light, but there are others. In the implementation at VSL, the lowest integration is set and a rotating wheel of attenuation filters adapts to the changing output pulse energy of the Ekspla laser as a function of wavelength. Once the attenuation is set at each wavelength, the integration time is increased 2 additional times ranging from 50 times the initial integration time in an intermediate step to up to 70 or 100 times at maximum. The setup is automated to perform these measurements.

The Spectral Distribution Function (SDF) was derived by normalizing each LSF by the sum of the counts in the in-band region of pixels around the laser wavelength. Assembling the LSFs into a square matrix using interpolation maps the stray light across the detector array. The spectral stray light correction matrix is derived from the inverse of the SDF matrix. A user can apply this correction matrix to the spectroradiometer's measurement signals to correct for stray light effects. The correction matrix must be optimized by varying parameters of the SDF analysis such as in-band region width and dark signal drift before and after measurement of each LSF.

The LSF dataset can also be utilized for a bandpass correction [1], [2], [10]. The correction requires the full width half maximum of LSFs from the pixels sampled within the in-band regions around each input laser wavelengths. This is the instrumental bandwidth of the spectroradiometer and can be found at various positions in the detector array. There the instrumental bandwidth can be used in the bandwidth correction via a fitted bandpass function found using the LSFs.

11.3.4 Spectral irradiance responsivity

At a fixed integration time with a maximum around 58,000 dark-corrected counts in the ADC when the lamp and entrance plane of the Varius spectroradiometer's fiber couple integrating sphere are aligned at the working distance of 50 cm of the certified lamp irradiance. The certified values of the lamp standard irradiance within the spectral measurement range of the spectroradiometer are combined with the instrument's output signal in counts when observing the lamps as measured in each pixel of the detector array.

11.4 Results of characterizations

11.4.1 Wavelength-pixel relation

The centroid pixel estimates against reference wavelength needed for the calculation of the spectral scale polynomial relation of the spectroradiometers in the digital twin model are presented in the top panels of Figure 57 and Figure 58.

Figure 57: 3rd degree polynomial fit, with residuals. Red lines have been placed at +/- 0.1 nm.

Figure 58: 3rd degree polynomial fit, with residuals. Red lines have been placed at +/- 0.1 nm.

The polynomial relations provide the wavelength pixel solution, which was used to determine the average spectral pixel spacing of the instruments. The average pixel-to-pixel distance was found to be 0.46 nm. Larger residuals at wavelengths below 400 nm could be due to the bandpass functions of these instruments or due to the emission lamp stability or their reference wavelength values used in the fitting.

Figure 59: Difference in the degree 3 polynomial solutions 7415927SP-7415925SP found by VSL (left), and a comparison of the wavelength-pixel relation of the instruments as delivered by Avantes to VSL to that found by VSL (right.)

11.4.2 Nonlinearity

From the variable attenuator-based setup, each instrument's readings were compared to the monitor detectors in order to calculate the nonlinearity or deviation from linearity. To this data degree 7 polynomials were fit for each instrument in this project. These fits included only the deviation from linearity found between 800 counts to 64,000 counts. This cut was made to prevent excessive oscillations in the fits presented below. The

deviations also significantly increase at the lower limit (near zero) and upper limit (near saturation) justifying this cut.

The error bars which appear in the plots in Figure 60 include uncertainty estimates for both the standard deviation in the monitor detector and in the Varius instrument readings.

Figure 60: Deviation from linearity for the two Varius instruments characterized in this project at VSL. Both data series were normalized to around the 40,000 dark-corrected counts level, as shown by their zero crossing at this value. Significant deviation from linearity is found below about 800 counts and above about 64,000 counts (dark corrected). Therefore, these regions of the data series were not included in the respective degree 7 polynomial fits shown in black.

The exact values of the coefficients of these fits depends on the lower and upper limits over which to fit. The coefficients (and therefore the nonlinearity correction) also depend on the counts level at which the data series is normalized to. These conditions for this data set have been laid out above. The measurement points in Figure 60 are those proposed by VSL to be used for the nonlinearity in the digital twin model.

Normalizing the polynomial fits in Figure 60 to their respective maxima, a comparison to the manufacturer's calibration can be made. The comparison is only for demonstration. The comparison uses the coefficients as delivered to VSL which are also a polynomial of degree 7 used for correction. This comparison to the re-normalized VSL functions are shown in Figure 61.

Figure 61: Comparison of the correction function for nonlinearity as delivered to VSL by Avantes for each instrument and the correction derived by VSL based on the fixed integration time method at VSL (after renormalizing to the maximum.) There seems to be better agreement in the corrections derived for the 7415927SP instrument.

11.4.3 Spectral stray light and bandpass

11.4.3.1 Line spread functions

The average spacing between the sampled LSFs in the first instrument (7415925SP) was 16 nm in the range 245 nm to 1111 nm with 56 LSFs measured, and the average spacing between the sampled LSFs in the second instrument (7415927SP) was 27 nm in the range 225 nm to 1111 nm with 35 LSFs measured.

Some of these LSFs measured in each instrument have been selected in Figure 62 and Figure 64 in to show near field and far field stray light features and how they differ between the two nominally identical instruments. The selected LSFs in Figure 63 also show the effect of lengthening the integration time in the characterization of the second of the two instruments' LSFs.

Differences in near field stray light features between instruments:

Figure 62: LSF measured with an excitation from the Ekspla OPO laser at 270 nm. This shows possible differences in the near field stray light features from 270 nm to 500 nm of the two instruments characterized, when the same integration times for each.

Effect of integration time used in the high dynamic range measurements:

The integration times used in the measurements of LSFs in 7415927SP were adjusted to improve the detection of the very small far field stray light features on the detector array observed in the 7415925SP. For example, in the intermediate level integration times (typically around 500 ms), the value was increased by about 40 % in the measurements of the 74127SP. And at the longest integration times (typically around 7 seconds), the value was sometimes increased by about 200 % to 350 % in the measurements of the second of the two instruments. Lastly, whereas the majority of the LSF measurements used 10 ms at the lowest of the integration times, significantly higher integration times were needed to account for the lower output pulse energy regions (see section 11.5) to make enough of the in-band profile of the LSF observable. This meant increasing the lowest integration time to 50 ms or 2 seconds, particularly for the LSFs measured at 225 nm and 245 nm.

Figure 63: LSF measured with an excitation from the Ekspla OPO laser at 300 nm, 405 nm and 505 nm. This shows that the average value of the near field stray light features of the two instruments characterized are better determined when measuring with longer integration times.

Differences in far field (and near field) stray light features:

Figure 64: LSF measured with an excitation from the Ekspla OPO laser at 345 nm, 385 nm, 695 nm, 715 nm, 915nm and 1111 nm. These plots shows differences in both the near field and far field stray light features of the two instruments characterized. The LSF at 715 nm (middle, right) shows a near field stray light feature peak observed at 715 nm in both instruments, whereas the LSF at 695 nm (middle, left) shows difference in the far field stray light at around 200 nm. The final plot (bottom right) also shows a possible faulty dark correction in instrument 7415925SP.

11.4.3.2 Stray light distribution functions

The measured LSFs are composed in a matrix form by interpolating the wavelengths of the laser radiation to the corresponding pixels and interpolating at all wavelengths in between. The dynamic range in the plots of stray light distribution functions have been limited to 10^{-3} to 10^{-7} (with the in-band portion removed) in order to better display stray light features in Figure 65 and Figure 66. All pixel values of each LSF measurement were normalized by the sum of the counts in its in-band region.

Stray light features have been resolved to different levels in each instrument as characterized at VSL, as shown by the lower right side of each of the plots below. In the first instrument characterized (Figure 65) the features below the diagonal appear to have been resolved better than in the second instrument (Figure 66.) However in the upper left of each of the plots when each of the instrument's detectors are excited by roughly 600 nm to 1000 nm laser radiation, similar features can be seen in both instruments at, and below, the 10^{-5} level in the IB counts normalized SDFs.

In the plots below, the in-band region has a full base width of 18 nm and shows both near field and fair field stray light features. In further calculations, this value is used for the correction derived from these stray light distribution functions.

Figure 65: SDFs for spectroradiometer 7415925SP, with linear interpolation to fill the pixels not sampled. In total 56 LSFs were sampled from 245 nm to 1111 nm. All values below 245 nm and above 1111nm are extrapolated.

Figure 66: SDFs for spectroradiometer 7415927SP, with linear interpolation to fill the pixels not sampled. In total 35 LSFs were sampled from 225 nm to 1111 nm. All values below 225 nm and above 1111 nm are extrapolated.

11.4.3.3 Spectral stray light correction matrices

The spectral stray light correction matrices are not shown here but are calculated from the matrices shown in the plots in section 11.4.3.2. The condition number of the matrix, as prescribed in [7], to be inverted was found to be stable and constant at about 1.1 and 1.3, for each of the respective instruments. To do so, the pixel width of the in-band (IB) region was set to a constant value across the detector array of 40 pixels which equals a full base width of on average 18 nm.

11.4.3.4 Spectral bandwidth

The bandwidth of the instrument as a function of wavelength can be calculated from the LSFs measured in section 11.4.3.1. An estimate of the bandwidth is found by considering only the region around each bandpass within the full base width of 18 nm (not as shown in Figure 67).

Figure 67: Selected measured LSFs (same as those shown in section 11.4.3.1) in instrument 7415927SP showing asymmetric and irregular shapes of some bandpass functions compared to a Gaussian model assumption. The asymmetry is probably due to both the bandpass function and near field stray light features. The vertical axes have been compressed with a log-linear scale.

The plots show that the real line spread functions (those of LSFs also shows in section 11.4.3.1) are not symmetric about their center wavelength. Despite this, the calculated bandwidths assume they are symmetric and roughly Gaussian shaped as an approximation.

Figure 68: Bandwidths of the two spectroradiometers characterized, as a function of wavelength.

11.4.4 Spectral irradiance responsivity

Figure 69: Spectral irradiance responsivity functions for the two Varius instruments (top left, top right.) Uncertainty in the spectral irradiance responsivity (bottom left, bottom right.) Not yet included in this analysis are the contributions from the nonlinearity correction and from the application of the wavelength-pixel relation. The corrections derived in the previous sections were applied to the FEL lamp calibration measurement in the following order: dark subtraction, nonlinearity correction, spectral stray light correction, wavelength-relation, division by FEL lamp reference spectral irradiance values.

11.5 Lessons learned

- The integration times set in the Varius instrument for some saturated LSF measurements was possibly too short, the LSFs below 300 nm and above 1050 nm show this. An intermediate integration time is possibly not needed for the high dynamic range combination method, saving machine time.
- Additional attenuation filter wheel positions for the adaptive attenuation wheel used in the setup could be used to make the setup even more automated.
- The low output pulse energy of the Ekspla laser source in some spectral ranges provided extra challenges when measuring the LSFs. This was case below about 400 nm, but particularly below about 300 nm. This is expected behavior since the tuning of the laser below 405 nm changes the output to the second harmonics and sum-frequency generator output. The maximum pulse energy in this lower range becomes about an order of magnitude lower.
- Laser coherence effects due to speckle within the 2-inch integrating sphere used in the nonlinearity setup caused initial systematic measurement errors. Solutions for this were pointed out by members of the consortium and the method implemented at VSL was improved in the setup during the project to fix this.
- A finer step size was needed in the variable attenuator setup of the nonlinearity by fixed integration time setup at VSL. This improved setup (along with the mirror for removing speckle) led to more reproducible data sets, as shown in section 11.4.2.

12 Conclusion

This deliverable presents a comprehensive report on the characterization and calibration of the relevant instrumental properties of 21 array spectroradiometers to be qualified as spectral irradiance transfer standards, which can be done by comparison to the minimum requirements produced in the project. The instruments evaluated span more than five end-user applications across both scientific and industrial applications. With the work now completed and reported here, the project has successfully met its goal to support the development of a detector-based approach for traceable spectral irradiance measurements.

The work was carried out by the consortium members, including the national metrology institutes, designated institutes, and instrument manufacturers from across Europe, and with support from the stakeholders, some of them as collaborators in the project. Radiometric characterisations and calibrations were performed on a range of commercially available array spectroradiometers. The consortium partners used well-established calibration and characterization methods to assess key properties of the instruments, such as pixel-to-wavelength assignment, nonlinearity of response, spectral stray light, bandpass, and measured spectral responsivity against existing secondary spectral irradiance standards. The characterisations provided data that are required for spectral correction functions of the respective radiometric properties of the instruments and for the assessment of the associated uncertainty contributions. The data is also used for the development and verification of the digital twin model. The estimated uncertainties in the spectral responsivity calibrations varied depending on the instrument, calibration method and spectral ranges, with lowest typical values ranging from around 0,5 % to 3.7 %. The results summarised in the report demonstrate that the objectives 2 and 3 of the project are reachable.

The results in the deliverable also underpin the development of the digital twin of the characterized instruments as tools to enable traceable irradiance measurements at end-user sites by estimating the measurement uncertainty for a detector-based traceability framework. Therefore, the results from this deliverable mark a significant milestone in the NEWSTAND project in terms of upcoming deliverables involving interlaboratory comparisons, good practice guides, and the implementation of digital twin model.

Beyond the technical content, this deliverable report includes many practical lessons learned through the calibrations performed. The openly shared information by the project partners in this deliverable may serve as a shared technical reference that supports the next phases of the project. For example, lessons learned include instrument-specific challenges requiring collaboration between project partners and stakeholders, the development of measurement setups and procedures performed at the project partners' laboratories, and the importance of order of calibration steps. These insights will feed into the upcoming best practice guides improving the project's proposed methods.

13 References

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